

A classical proof system for quantum unsatisfiability, based on a matrix Nullstellensatz*

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Abstract

We define the first nontrivial proof system for the *complement* of quantum satisfiability ($\overline{\text{QSAT}}$). The system uses left-ideal rules in the ring of linear operators on an n -qubit register. Implicational completeness is given by a matricial version of Hilbert’s Nullstellensatz. We prove two distinct forms of the system to be equivalent respectively to Resolution and Polynomial Calculus with Resolution in the classical subcase.

The systems are efficiently verifiable by a classical TM. We also discuss the matter of *quantum* proof systems for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$.

1 Introduction

The fundamental ‘Cook–Levin theorem’ [15] efficiently maps a deterministic algorithm for a classical computing machine to a set of propositional logic formulas, such that their conjunction is satisfiable iff there exists an input leading the algorithm to acceptance. With the same idea, but more involved technical details, Kitaev [27] first mapped a general quantum computation to a set of projectors on a quantum register, such that their sum is unfrustrated iff there exists an initial quantum state that leads the computation to certain acceptance.

The problem of determining, given a set of projectors on the Hilbert space of an n -qubit register, whether their sum is *not* frustrated, will be called quantum satisfiability in the following, and denoted QSAT. It can be seen as a generalization of the classical satisfiability problem (SAT); and has a very natural quantum proof system, where the certificate is a quantum state in the common nullspace of the projectors.

The quantum version of the Cook–Levin theorem implies that QSAT captures the complexity of general quantum verifications with perfect completeness [22] (the \mathcal{QM}_1 class¹), much like SAT captures the \mathcal{NP} class.

Proof systems for the *complementary* problem, i.e. unsatisfiability, have been extensively studied in the classical subcase ($\overline{\text{SAT}}$), in particular by proof complexity [29]. It is conjectured that an efficiently verifiable proof system with a polynomial upper bound on the length of certificates (a so-called ‘super’ proof system) cannot exist for $\overline{\text{SAT}}$, but proving it would be extremely difficult as

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¹Note that (bounded) error allowance on the completeness side has been shown to be inessential for proof systems in the probabilistic classical case both for interactive and non-interactive proofs [18], in the quantum case for interactive proofs [28], and in the quantum case for non-interactive proofs with classical certificates [26]. Still, it is not known whether $\mathcal{QM}_1 = \mathcal{QMA}$: see [1] for an authoritative discussion of this difficult open question.

it implies $\mathcal{NP} \neq \mathcal{P}$. In the general quantum case, one can always decide the problem through direct nullspace calculations, involving $2^n \times 2^n$ matrices; but a nontrivial proof system has not yet been proposed, for either classical or quantum verification.

We present the first classical proof system for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$. We call it ‘Matricial Calculus’ (MC), as it closely resembles the proof system for $\overline{\text{SAT}}$ known as ‘Polynomial Calculus’ (PC) [14]. Both PC and MC use ideal operations as deduction rules, but in different rings. They lie in the rings of multivariate polynomials and square matrices respectively. Matrices are, of course, noncommutative; so left, right and two-sided ideals do not coincide in general. Since we consider, as it is customary in quantum notation, operators acting from the left on column vectors (kets), we will use *left* ideals for MC. In dealing with classical logic formulas, PC takes as axioms the polynomials $x_i^2 - x_i$, for each variable x_i ; these allow, syntactically, the reduction of every polynomial to its multilinear version, and, semantically, ensure the restriction to the Boolean domain. MC requires no axioms, since the nullspaces of the matrices directly represent the desired semantics, and there is a perfect correspondence between subspaces and left-ideals in the matrix ring. Completeness of PC is usually derived by Hilbert’s Nullstellensatz, despite much less involved mathematics being actually needed; we prove an elementary ‘strong Nullstellensatz’ for matrices, that works in any field: it suffices for *implicational* completeness of both MC and PC. From any set of matrices, representing the initial hypotheses, MC can deduce any matrix that annihilates their common nullspace. In particular, if it derives the unit matrix, it means that the hypotheses lead to a contradiction: they have no common nullspace. In the case of a set of projectors on a quantum register, they are an instance of $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$. In quantum logic, where proper statements stand for subspaces of a semantic Hilbert space [9], projectors are naturally taken as algebraic counterparts of subspaces. If we identify the nullspace of a projector as the set of states where the corresponding quantum statement is true with certainty, and an instance of $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$ as the logical conjunction of its projectors, then MC deduces from them any quantum logic consequence. Since we can identify Boolean functions with *diagonal* projectors on a quantum register, MC works as well for classical logic. We prove that its strength as a proof system for classical logic is equivalent to that of the well-known ‘Resolution’ proof system (R). Consequently it has, for example, an exponential lower bound for the ‘pigeonhole principle’ [24].

More generally, the MC proof system applies to any set of initial matrices. In particular it can be used to prove that a local Hamiltonian is frustrated: a central subproblem in the field of ‘Hamiltonian complexity’, highly relevant to both computer science and theoretical physics [20].

The key complexity parameter of MC is the locality of the matrices involved in the derivation. The representation of any k -local matrix takes length $\mathcal{O}(4^k)$. So an optimal MC derivation will keep locality as low as possible, in order to minimize its length. Of course, it is not possible in general to keep matrices local; otherwise, it would be $\overline{\text{QSAT}} \in \mathcal{NP}$ since an MC proof is verifiable in polynomial time by a classical TM. We prove that, on classical CNF formulas, MC’s locality and Resolution’s width exactly simulate each other.

We also define a slight modification of MC, that gives it more power. This enhanced proof system (MC+) is equivalent to ‘Polynomial Calculus with Resolution’ (PCR) on classical formulas.

Finally, we consider the idea of a *quantum* proof system. Very natural quantum proof systems [38] exist for problems related to upper-bounding the ground energy of local Hamiltonians, whereas in general classical proof systems with polynomially long certificates appear insufficient for this task. We don’t know, however, how a quantum system can help with the complementary problem of *lower*-bounding the ground energy. Thus, even just conceiving a genuine quantum proof system for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$ would need a new conjectured quantum supremacy. After decades of research, the examples

of exponential advantages of quantum computation over classical Turing machines remain relatively scarce (for a good list of quantum algorithms and applications see the introductory book [36] and its references). Therefore a quantum version of MC would be a major discovery in the field.

In the case of classical logic, Pudlák [33] proposed a “quantum version” of classical Frege systems. However one can argue that Pudlák’s idea does not constitute a genuine quantum proof system as characterized by the concept of quantum verification classes. Moreover, the approach of applying quantum proof systems to *classical* logic has an additional difficulty. His aim is ‘to initiate the study of quantum concepts in proof complexity’; but the central goal of proof complexity, i.e. proving that TAUT, or $\overline{\text{SAT}}$, cannot have a super proof system, becomes even more challenging when extended to quantum systems, which include classical ones as a special case. Considering classical proof systems for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$, such as the MC system, provides the mirrored advantage: since $\overline{\text{SAT}} \subset \overline{\text{QSAT}}$, proving $\overline{\text{QSAT}} \notin \mathcal{NP}$ is in principle easier, and could be a step toward $\overline{\text{SAT}} \notin \mathcal{NP}$ (which, we recall, is more difficult than $\mathcal{NP} \neq \mathcal{P}$).

Quantum proof systems for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$ are instead relevant for the class coQMA_1 . We fall short of actually conceiving such a system. But we generalize to quantum verification classes the famous Cook–Reckhow observation [16] (which initiated the area of research we now call proof complexity) that $\text{coNP} = \mathcal{NP}$ is equivalent to the existence of a super proof system for TAUT. And we discuss analogies and differences with the classical case.

1.1 Organization

In Section 2 we fix the base concepts and notations, and define the quantum satisfiability/unsatisfiability problem. It is also insightful to briefly frame the problem in the purview of quantum logic (Section 3).

We describe the MC proof system in Section 5. Its implicational soundness and completeness derive from the strong algebra-geometry connection in a ring of matrices: we explicitly address that, preliminarily, in Section 4. In order to better understand MC, in Section 5.1 we study at length its restriction to diagonal matrices (DMC), which encompass the more familiar case of classical formulas; and we compare it with Resolution on CNF instances: in Section 5.2 we construct reciprocal polynomial simulations between the two systems.

The MC+ strengthening of our matricial proof system is defined in Section 6. Via a natural bijection between diagonal matrices and multilinear polynomials, we prove that the restriction of MC+ to diagonal matrices (DMC+) is equivalent to Polynomial Calculus with Resolution. We also discuss the automatizability of general MC+ proofs, in Section 7; extending the original PC proof search algorithm in [14] to the non-diagonal case.

The proof systems defined in this paper are classical, although we also briefly address, in Section 9, the topic of *quantum* proof systems for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$ from a general complexity theory perspective. We apply the classical proof complexity approach to the quantum world, and we compare the two versions; a direction first investigated by [31], and recently suggested in [6]. Before that, it is insightful to critically review, in Section 8, the only work in literature (by our knowledge) about quantum proof systems in proof complexity: the 16 years old paper [33] by Pavel Pudlák.

2 The Problem

We assume the reader is familiar with all the basics of proof complexity, quantum computation and quantum proofs [29][36][38]. However, in order to establish our notation and lexicon, we will recall

in this section the elementary concepts and definitions needed to describe a quantum generalization of the space of classical truth assignments and introduce the problem of quantum unsatisfiability.

2.1 Quantum Semantics

A QUBIT is a unit vector $|\psi\rangle$ in an inner product space \mathbb{C}^2 , with an orthonormal basis denoted $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$:

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle \quad \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* = 1$$

Having more than one qubit, we shall denote the i -th qubit by $|\psi_i\rangle$ and its space by \mathbb{C}_i^2 . An n -qubit REGISTER is a set

$$S = \{|\psi_1\rangle, |\psi_2\rangle, \dots, |\psi_n\rangle\}$$

of n labeled qubits. An ASSIGNMENT for S is a unit vector

$$|\Psi\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i |X_i\rangle \quad \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \alpha_i^* = 1$$

in the

$$N = 2^n$$

dimensional tensor product space

$$\mathcal{S} = \mathbb{C}_1^2 \otimes \mathbb{C}_2^2 \otimes \dots \otimes \mathbb{C}_n^2$$

of the n qubits; having orthonormal basis $\{|X_1\rangle, |X_2\rangle, \dots, |X_N\rangle\}$, where

$$|X\rangle = |x_1\rangle |x_2\rangle \dots |x_n\rangle \quad x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{B}$$

We call these basis vectors **BOOLEAN ASSIGNMENTS**, as they correspond to the assignments of n classical bits (succinctly denoted using single capital X letters); we also equivalently denote Boolean assignments by $|x_1 x_2 \dots x_n\rangle$. Of course, a general quantum assignment for the register is not an assignment for every qubit: due to entanglement, a state of the composite system may not coincide with any tensor product of components' states. Note also that, for $|\Psi\rangle$ an assignment, we always have

$$|\Psi\rangle \neq 0 \quad (2.1)$$

A k -qubit register ($k \leq n$) of the type

$$L = \{|\psi_{i_1}\rangle, |\psi_{i_2}\rangle, \dots, |\psi_{i_k}\rangle\} \quad |\psi_{i_1}\rangle, |\psi_{i_2}\rangle, \dots, |\psi_{i_k}\rangle \in S$$

is said a **SUBREGISTER** of S . For its space

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathbb{C}_{i_1}^2 \otimes \mathbb{C}_{i_2}^2 \otimes \dots \otimes \mathbb{C}_{i_k}^2$$

we say that it is a **LOCAL SPACE** of \mathcal{S} . Given a subregister $L \subseteq S$, there is a complementary subregister $L^c \subseteq S$ such that $L \cup L^c = S$; we denote its space by \mathcal{L}^c . With respect to \mathcal{L} , the basis states of a local space will be called **PARTIAL BOOLEAN ASSIGNMENTS**.

Finally, we explicitly address here the convention on the logical meaning of Boolean assignments: contrary to the more common notation, we adopt the values 1 and 0 to indicate respectively 'false' and 'true'. This is because we deal with proof systems whose deduction steps are ideal operations, and these preserve roots; i.e. the "dual" convention adopted naturally grants implicational soundness.

2.2 Matrix Representation

A generic linear operator p on the space \mathcal{S} can be explicitly given by

$$p = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j} |X_i\rangle \langle X_j| \quad (2.2)$$

Note that the matrix entries $\alpha_{i,j}$ that define a generic operator are \mathbb{C} numbers, while we need to express them by finite strings. We shall thus limit to p whose entries, for the real and imaginary parts, are \mathbb{Q} numbers² (for convenience such a field will be henceforth denoted simply as \mathbb{C}). Note also that, when most of the matrix entries are zero, the Dirac notation used in (2.2) can be exponentially shorter than representing p by its whole $N \times N$ matrix. We shall thus consider the matrices in the object proof system to always be expressed in Dirac notation with non-null terms only (the null matrix being denoted simply as the scalar 0). Note that ordinary matrix arithmetic in Dirac notation can be done efficiently with respect to the length of the matrices' expressions. Nonetheless, for graphical convenience in our exposition, we will also make use of common matrix representations with rows and columns; for which, though, we need to fix an ordering of the basis vectors: when not specified otherwise, the default labeling will be

$$|0\dots00\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad |0\dots01\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad |\dots010\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots \quad |1\dots11\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Given an operator P on a local space \mathcal{L} , we say that³

$$p = \underbrace{P}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes \underbrace{1}_{\mathcal{L}^c} \quad (2.3)$$

is k -LOCAL, where k is the number of qubits in the subregister of \mathcal{L} (which we call the k -LOCAL SPACE of p). Should we rearrange the basis vectors' labeling in blocks of assignments that differ only for the \mathcal{L} subregister, the matrix representation of p would be a constant block diagonal matrix with P on the diagonal⁴.

In any case p can be expressed by just the $\leq 4^k$ non-null terms of the LOCAL MATRIX P , along with the specification of the qubits to which the matrix applies. Writing P in Dirac notation, we have

$$p = \sum_{i=1}^{2^k} \sum_{j=1}^{2^k} \alpha_{i,j} |P_i\rangle\langle P_j| \otimes 1 \quad (2.4)$$

where the $|P_i\rangle$ vectors are the Boolean assignments of the local space \mathcal{L} (partial Boolean assignments of \mathcal{S}). We say that (2.4) expresses p in k -local form.

Of course, we can also express p in a $(k+1)$ -local space $\mathcal{L} \otimes \mathbb{C}_i^2$, for any \mathbb{C}_i^2 that is not a local space of \mathcal{L} :

$$p = \underbrace{P'}_{\mathcal{L} \otimes \mathbb{C}_i^2} \otimes 1$$

²Of course all the projectors resulting from the circuit to Hamiltonian mapping by the quantum Cook-Levin theorem are comprehended, unless the gates themselves have irrational entries. It has long been known [2] that irrationals are not required for universal quantum computation, although commonly used quantum gates such as the 'Hadamard gate' and the $\pi/4$ 'phase gate' have $\sqrt{2}$ factors. To cover such cases, one only needs to add a symbol for $\sqrt{2}$ to the field.

³In the following we shall often avoid the space subscripts in tensor products when it can be easily understood how the space is partitioned.

⁴

$$p = \begin{bmatrix} P & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & P & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & & & \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & P \end{bmatrix}$$

The P' local matrix just duplicates the entries of P for labels $|P_i, 0\rangle\langle P_j, 0|$ and $|P_i, 1\rangle\langle P_j, 1|$, i.e.

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^{2^k} \sum_{j=1}^{2^k} \alpha_{i,j} (|P_i, 0\rangle\langle P_j, 0| + |P_i, 1\rangle\langle P_j, 1|) \otimes 1 \quad (2.5)$$

where

$$|P, x_i\rangle = \underbrace{|P\rangle}_{\mathcal{L}} \underbrace{|x_i\rangle}_{\mathbb{C}_i^2}$$

Vice versa, if a $(k+1)$ -local matrix happens to have the (2.5) form, then it is (also) a k -local matrix, and can be expressed more simply by (2.4). Note that both the expansion (2.4) \mapsto (2.5) and the reduction (2.5) \mapsto (2.4) can be computed efficiently with respect to the length of the Dirac expression of the local matrix.

2.3 Quantum Formulas

An instance of the quantum satisfiability problem, shortly we will say a quantum formula, is a set

$$f = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\} \quad (2.6)$$

of orthogonal projectors (but one commonly says simply ‘projectors’) on \mathcal{L} . An assignment $|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{L}$ is said to SATISFY f iff it is a solution⁵ of the system

$$\begin{cases} p_1 |\Psi\rangle = 0 \\ p_2 |\Psi\rangle = 0 \\ \vdots \\ p_s |\Psi\rangle = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.7)$$

As described in Section 3, we can interpret the p_i as quantum logic propositions about the semantic space \mathcal{L} . Contrary to the usual convention, we assume here 0 as the ‘true’ value, and 1 as ‘false’. Then we can naturally interpret the formula f as the logical conjunction of the p_i constraints. Satisfiable formulas, whose set we denote by QSAT, are those for which system (2.7) has $|\Psi\rangle \neq 0$ solutions; we denote by $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$ the set of contradictions, i.e. formulas f for which system (2.7) has only the trivial (and non-physical) $|\Psi\rangle = 0$ solution; we denote by $k\text{QSAT}$ ($\overline{k\text{QSAT}}$) the intersection of QSAT ($\overline{\text{QSAT}}$) with the set of formulas whose projectors are expressed in k' -local form, with $k' \leq k$. Hence

$$k'\text{QSAT} \subseteq k\text{QSAT} \qquad \overline{k'\text{QSAT}} \subseteq \overline{k\text{QSAT}}$$

for every

$$k' \leq k$$

A different perspective is given by the study of the observable

$$H_f = \sum_{i=1}^s p_i \quad (2.8)$$

The mean value $\langle \Psi | H_f | \Psi \rangle$ of a measure of H_f in state $|\Psi\rangle$ gives the “number” of p_i unsatisfied by $|\Psi\rangle$: the sum of the mean values of measures of the p_i in $|\Psi\rangle$. We clearly have

$$0 \leq \varepsilon_{\min} \leq \langle \Psi | H_f | \Psi \rangle \leq \varepsilon_{\max} \leq s$$

where ε_{\min} (ε_{\max}) are the minimum (maximum) eigenvalues of H_f . We can exploit a physical terminology, by considering H_f a Hamiltonian operator. A Hamiltonian of the type (2.8) is in general frustrated. Unlike p_i eigenvalues, energy levels are not necessarily integers. But system

⁵Remembering (2.1).

(2.7) has a ($|\Psi\rangle \neq 0$) solution iff $\varepsilon_{\min} = 0$. Thus we can see the satisfiability problem for the formula (2.6) as a spectral problem for the Hamiltonian (2.8). This “physical” formulation is the standard one in the literature; and it naturally generalizes to the problem of bounding ε_{\min} for nonzero values: the quantum analogue of the ‘maximum satisfiability’ problem (we will touch on this broader problem only in Section 9).

3 Quantum Logic

The birth of quantum logic is commonly attributed to a 1936 article by Garrett Birkhoff and John von Neumann [17, 9]. Their starting point is a peculiar semantics, suited for logics supposed to refer to quantum mechanical systems. The proposal of Birkhoff and von Neumann, from which the whole labyrinth [25] of mathematical systems investigated under the general rubric of quantum logic develops, is that proper statements⁶ about a quantum mechanical system S should identify *subspaces* of its Hilbert space \mathcal{S} , not just generic subsets of \mathcal{S} . This request appears fairly grounded from an epistemologically “empiricist” point of view. A meaningful statement should be, in principle, experimentally verifiable, and thus ultimately refer only to observable values. More generally, a proper statement about a quantum mechanical system S specifies the eigenvalues (the experimental outcomes) for a given set of compatible observables, and it is properly true only in the states of its Hilbert space \mathcal{S} that are common eigenvectors of those eigenvalues; these constitute, as we know [32], a closed subspace of \mathcal{S} . We can usefully limit observables to be orthogonal projector operators, also called PROPERTIES. In fact any observable can be expressed, by spectral decomposition, in terms of orthogonal projectors onto its eigenspaces. Moreover, since any closed subspace is the eigenspace of some projector, a quantum logical statement ultimately specifies that some quantum property holds (that it has value 1). The statement is true in those states where an ideal measure’s outcome is determined (and confirms the statement); that is, in the eigenvectors of the 1 eigenvalue.

For the purposes of the present paper it is opportune to adopt the “dual” convention: we represent a quantum property that is true in the states of

$$\mathcal{P} \subseteq \mathcal{S}$$

(and only in those states) by the projector

$$p|\Psi\rangle = \begin{cases} 0 & |\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{P} \\ |\Psi\rangle & |\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{P}^\perp \end{cases}$$

Thus the property holds not in the range but in the *nullspace* of p (coherently with the truth value convention we adopted in Section 2).

As in classical logic, a natural entailment relation is defined by set inclusion in the semantic space. Let a, b be two properties with subspaces respectively $\mathcal{P}_a, \mathcal{P}_b \subseteq \mathcal{S}$; if and only if $\mathcal{P}_a \subseteq \mathcal{P}_b$, then in every state in which a is true also b is true, and we write $a \models b$. We denote by $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ the logical poset defined, on the set of properties of \mathcal{S} , by the \models relation. The greatest and least elements of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ with respect to the entailment ordering are the constant properties associated with the whole space and the null vector respectively, i.e. the 0,1 scalar projectors.

It is not necessary here to elaborate on $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ except for recalling a few elementary concepts: we refer the reader to the standard textbook [34] for a self-contained introduction. In this paper \mathcal{S} is the Hilbert space of an n -qubit register; in particular \mathcal{S} is a *finite*-dimensional space, so closure

⁶Being intended only to capture the static “structure” of a physical system S , statements are here independent of the specific laws governing S , in the sense that they tell us nothing about the system’s evolution.

conditions hold automatically. In this case it is well known that $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ forms a modular, non-distributive lattice. The meet and join $a \sqcap b$, $a \sqcup b$ of two properties $a, b \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$, which represent their logical conjunction and disjunction respectively, are semantically associated with the subsets:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_{a \sqcap b} &= \{|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{S} : (|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{P}_a) \wedge (|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{P}_b)\} \\ &= \mathcal{P}_a \cap \mathcal{P}_b \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_{a \sqcup b} &= \{|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{S} : (\exists |\Psi_a\rangle \in \mathcal{P}_a, |\Psi_b\rangle \in \mathcal{P}_b) (|\Psi\rangle = |\Psi_a\rangle + |\Psi_b\rangle)\} \\ &\supseteq \mathcal{P}_a \cup \mathcal{P}_b \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

A natural orthocomplementation on $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ corresponds to logical negation: given a property a , associated with \mathcal{P}_a , the property \tilde{a} is associated with \mathcal{P}_a^\perp :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_{\tilde{a}} &= \{|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{S} : |\Psi\rangle \perp \mathcal{P}_a\} \\ &\subsetneq \overline{\mathcal{P}_a} \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

We put in evidence the comparison with classical logic semantics.

Finally, let's recast the quantum satisfiability problem, defined in Section 2.3, on the lattice of quantum properties $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$. Asking whether system (2.7) has a nontrivial solution is equivalent to asking whether the subspaces associated with properties $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ have a nontrivial intersection; i.e., for (3.1), whether $p_1 \sqcap p_2 \sqcap \dots \sqcap p_s \neq 1$.

3.1 Classical Logic as a Special Case

We map every classical formula of propositional logic to a corresponding projector on the space \mathcal{S} of an n -qubit register, in the following way. Let p be the formula and $\{X_{i_1}, X_{i_2}, \dots, X_{i_m}\}$ the set of its satisfying assignments, we take p (in Roman) as the projector associated with the subspace \mathcal{P} spanned by $\{|X_{i_1}\rangle, |X_{i_2}\rangle, \dots, |X_{i_m}\rangle\}$ (thus p projects onto \mathcal{P}^\perp , and \mathcal{P} is its nullspace).

Note that, since Boolean assignments $|X_i\rangle$ are orthonormal basis vectors of \mathcal{S} , the matrix expressing p is diagonal, with entries in \mathbb{B} . Conversely, every diagonal matrix with entries in \mathbb{B} is a projector with nullspace spanned by Boolean assignments, so it's the matrix of some Boolean formula: of any formula whose truth table matches the diagonal of the matrix.

It is then straightforward to verify, considering the semantical definition (3.3), that the quantum property corresponding to the negation $\neg a$ of a Boolean formula a is the orthocomplementation \tilde{a} of the quantum property corresponding to a . And, considering (3.1), (3.2), that the quantum properties corresponding to the conjunction $a \wedge b$ and disjunction $a \vee b$ of two Boolean formulas a, b are respectively the meet $a \sqcap b$ and join $a \sqcup b$ of the quantum properties corresponding to a, b . Also note that classical tautologies and contradictions are mapped to the extremes of the $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ lattice, i.e. to the 0,1 scalar properties respectively.

To emphasize the interpretation of classical logic expressions as operations in the broader lattice of projectors on an n -qubit register, we will use meet and join symbols \sqcap, \sqcup for logical connectives. This allows us to consistently adopt the same logical symbols for both the classical and quantum cases.

Now take a classical formula f , in the form

$$f = p_1 \sqcap p_2 \sqcap \dots \sqcap p_s$$

(w.l.g. since at worst we have only one p , i.e. $f=p$); and let p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s be the projectors translating the Boolean formulas p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s as explained above. The classical satisfiability problem for f is equivalent to asking whether $p_1 \sqcap p_2 \sqcap \dots \sqcap p_s \neq 1$; which, as we have seen, is equivalent to the quantum satisfiability problem defined in Section 2.3. Thus, denoting by $\text{SAT}, \overline{\text{SAT}}$ the sets of all quantum

formulas translating the respective classical formulas, we have

$$\text{SAT} \subset \text{QSAT} \qquad \overline{\text{SAT}} \subset \overline{\text{QSAT}}$$

Of course the translation alone can be, in general, computationally hard. But we will see that, when the p_i are clauses, or more generally in polynomial form, the translation is trivial; and this will enable our matricial proof systems to efficiently simulate weak systems like Resolution or Polynomial Calculus.

Remark. We have to stress that the purview adopted in this paper is somewhat unusual in quantum logic. In particular, it is more frequent in the literature to see a satisfiable formula defined as a lattice expression that allows a choice of the properties not yielding the least of the lattice⁷. In such case quantum contradictions are, for the same reason that Hilbert lattices contain Boolean sublattices, a proper *subset* of classical ones. This approach is more relevant for the original interest in quantum logic, which was primarily aimed to an axiomatic formulation of quantum mechanics based on the general properties of the quantum logical connectives (see [17]). Our perspective instead aligns with concepts from the field of quantum complexity; and, as argued in [31], it is better suited for studying the relations between quantum logic and quantum computation, generalizing the relations between classical logic and classical computation.

4 Matrix Nullstellensatz

Let $\mathbb{M}_N(\mathbb{F})$ be the ring of square matrices of dimension $N \times N$ over a field \mathbb{F} . The first difference with polynomial rings is that $\mathbb{M}_N(\mathbb{F})$ for any $N \geq 2$ is, of course, non-commutative. This implies that we have to distinguish left, right and two-sided ideals. Since our interest is to deal with systems of the type (2.7) in view of a generalization of the classical proof systems based on the Nullstellensatz, we shall limit our investigation to the *left* ideals of $\mathbb{M}_N(\mathbb{F})$. Indeed, a vector $|\Psi\rangle$ in the nullspace of a matrix $p \in \mathbb{M}_N(\mathbb{F})$, is also in the nullspace of any matrix qp , with $q \in \mathbb{M}_N(\mathbb{F})$; but not necessarily in the nullspace of pq , if $[p,q] \neq 0$. Moreover, since our matrices are linear operators on the Hilbert space of a quantum register, our field of interest is \mathbb{C} .

In polynomial rings, ideals of the kind

$$I_Z = \{p \in \mathbb{C}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] : (\forall X \in Z)(p(X) = 0)\} \qquad Z \subseteq \mathbb{C}^n$$

defined semantically from a set of roots Z , do not generally form a *lattice* (see [31]). Although this is actually the case for ideals containing the polynomials $x_i^2 - x_i$, which force the roots to be Boolean; and this gives a perfect correspondence (implicational soundness and implicational completeness) between the syntax and the semantics of the algebraic proof systems for classical logic based on the Nullstellensatz.

Compared to $\mathbb{C}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, the analogous algebra-geometry relation in a matrix ring is even tighter, as we shall see in this section; and we can define (in Sections 5 and 6) natural generalizations of the Nullstellensatz proof systems, applicable to the quantum formulas defined in Section 2.3.

Unlike polynomial rings, we nowhere need to assume that the field \mathbb{F} of $\mathbb{M}_N(\mathbb{F})$ is algebraically closed. We shall often denote $\mathbb{M}_N(\mathbb{F})$ simply by R , and refer to it as the ‘matrix ring’. Correspondingly, we denote the vector space \mathbb{F}^N simply by \mathcal{S} . Our field of reference is, of course, \mathbb{C} ; and the vector space is the 2^n -dimensional Hilbert space of a quantum register of n qubits. But the results

⁷Note that, in quantum formulas as we defined them in Section 2.3, the $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{S})$ elements are fixed; the “variable” is the quantum state $|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{S}$, which corresponds to a Boolean assignment in the classical case.

of this section will be pretty general. Moreover, by considering the matrices as operators on the dual space of \mathcal{S} , one can easily transpose the following analysis to work for right ideals.

Results are significantly easier than in polynomial rings, allowing for a brief and straightforward treatment.

4.1 Preliminaries

Given a set I of matrices, let \mathcal{P}_I be the set of vectors that are in the nullspace of each matrix of I :

$$\mathcal{P}_I = \{|\Psi\rangle \in \mathcal{S} : (\forall p \in I)(p|\Psi\rangle = 0)\} \quad I \subseteq R \quad (4.1)$$

We call \mathcal{P}_I the COMMON NULLSPACE of the I matrices.

Due to the linearity of R elements as operators on vectors $|\Psi\rangle$, it is clear that \mathcal{P}_I is a *subspace* of \mathcal{S} . It is also straightforward to see that, if I in (4.1) is not itself an ideal, in any case $\mathcal{P}_I = \mathcal{P}_{\langle I \rangle}$ where $\langle I \rangle$ is the left ideal generated by I .

4.2 Results

Lemma 1. *Let*

$$p = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \Psi_1 | \\ \langle \Psi_2 | \\ \vdots \\ \langle \Psi_N | \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

be a matrix⁸ of R , then any matrix

$$a = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ 0 \\ \langle \Psi_i | \\ 0 \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}$$

with $\langle \Psi_i |$ on the j -th row is in the left ideal generated by p .

Proof. We have

$$a = qp$$

for

$$(q)_{r,c} = \delta_{r,j} \delta_{c,i}$$

where δ is the Kronecker delta. ■

So we can, by multiplication from the left, select at will a row and copy it in a row at will of the product. This has an immediate important corollary which will briefly provide us with a characterization of the left ideal generated by a matrix p , based solely on its nullspace \mathcal{P} .

Corollary 2. *Let p be the matrix (4.2), and let \mathcal{P}^\perp be the subspace spanned by $|\Psi_1\rangle, |\Psi_2\rangle, \dots, |\Psi_N\rangle$. Then any matrix*

$$a = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \Psi'_1 | \\ \langle \Psi'_2 | \\ \vdots \\ \langle \Psi'_N | \end{bmatrix}$$

⁸We mean, by notation (4.2), that the i, j entry of p is the j -th coordinate of $\langle \Psi_i |$.

with

$$|\Psi'_i\rangle \in \mathcal{P}^\perp \quad \forall i \quad (4.3)$$

is in the left ideal generated by \mathfrak{p} .

Proof. From (4.3) we have

$$|\Psi'_i\rangle = \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j} |\Psi_j\rangle \quad \langle \Psi'_i| = \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j}^* \langle \Psi_j|$$

for some scalars $\alpha_{i,j}$. Then, applying Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ 0 \\ \langle \Psi'_i| \\ 0 \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} &= \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j}^* \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ 0 \\ \langle \Psi_j| \\ 0 \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j}^* \mathfrak{q}_{i,j} \mathfrak{p} \end{aligned}$$

for some matrices $\mathfrak{q}_{i,j}$. And

$$\mathfrak{a} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_{i,j}^* \mathfrak{q}_{i,j} \mathfrak{p}$$

Thus \mathfrak{a} is in the left ideal generated by \mathfrak{p} . ■

Let I be the left ideal generated by a matrix $\mathfrak{p} \in R$. Clearly, the nullspace \mathcal{P}_a of any matrix $\mathfrak{a} \in I$ contains the nullspace \mathcal{P} of \mathfrak{p} . Corollary 2 tells us that also the reverse holds: if the nullspace \mathcal{P}_a of a matrix \mathfrak{a} contains \mathcal{P} , then $\mathfrak{a} \in I$. Indeed, the rows of a matrix (we mean the vectors $|\Psi_i\rangle \in \mathcal{S}$ corresponding to them) are clearly orthogonal to its nullspace; in fact they *span* the space orthogonal to the matrix nullspace⁹. Thus the row space \mathcal{P}^\perp in Corollary 2 is exactly the orthogonal complement of the nullspace of matrix (4.2); and the rows of \mathfrak{a} are in \mathcal{P}_a^\perp . So, if $\mathcal{P}_a \supseteq \mathcal{P}$, then $(\mathcal{P}_a^\perp \subseteq \mathcal{P}^\perp)$ the rows of \mathfrak{a} are in \mathcal{P}^\perp ; and Corollary 2 applies, giving $\mathfrak{a} \in I$. In summary, a matrix is in the left ideal generated by \mathfrak{p} if and only if it annihilates \mathcal{P} . In other words, the left ideal generated by a matrix consists precisely of those matrices that annihilate its nullspace.

We generalize this reasoning to any left ideal in the following theorem.

Theorem 3 (Matrix Nullstellensatz). *Let $I \subseteq R$ be a set of matrices. Then a matrix $\mathfrak{a} \in R$ is in the left ideal generated by I iff*

$$\mathcal{P}_a \supseteq \mathcal{P}_I \quad (4.4)$$

where \mathcal{P}_a is the nullspace of \mathfrak{a} and \mathcal{P}_I the common nullspace of I .

Proof. Let's assume (4.4) (the other direction is trivial). Then the rows of \mathfrak{a} are in \mathcal{P}_I^\perp . Since \mathcal{P}_I is, by definition, the space orthogonal to all the rows of all the matrices of I , then the rows of I span \mathcal{P}_I^\perp . In particular, since the space is finite-dimensional, \mathcal{P}_I^\perp must be generated by a finite number of rows, and thus a finite number of matrices, of I . From these matrices we can thus obtain matrix \mathfrak{a} , with a straightforward adaptation of the construction in the proof of Corollary 2. ■

4.3 Consequences

We can see Theorem 3 as a “strong Nullstellensatz” for matrices¹⁰. In particular, the left ideal generated by a set of matrices with no common nullspace, contains 1 and thus coincides with the

⁹A vector is in the nullspace iff it is orthogonal to each $|\Psi_i\rangle$.

¹⁰But here the connection between algebra and geometry is even stronger than in $\mathbb{C}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, because it holds for every ideal.

entire ring: the “weak Nullstellensatz” for matrices. The ideal membership problem can thus be reduced to common nullspace computations. Relevant to this paper, is the application of Theorem 3 in the opposite direction: we use $1 \in \langle p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s \rangle$ as a proof that system (2.7) has no solutions.

Also, every left ideal I can be generated by just the projector onto the subspace \mathcal{P}_I^\perp (or by any matrix with nullspace \mathcal{P}_I). The poset of left ideals of $M_N(\mathbb{F})$ is isomorphic to the lattice of subspaces of \mathbb{F}^N . In particular, when $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}$ and $N = 2^n$, to the lattice of subspaces of the Hilbert space of a register of n qubits, i.e. to the quantum logic lattice described in Section 3.

5 The Proof System (MC)

As a consequence of Theorem 3, given a set of projectors p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s , any projector p that is satisfied by all the quantum assignments that satisfy p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s can be obtained as $p = q_1 p_1 + q_2 p_2 + \dots + q_s p_s$, for some $q_1, q_2, \dots, q_s \in R$. That is, all (and only) the quantum logical consequences of the formula $f = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$ are obtainable through a finite succession of additions and left multiplications: a proof system for quantum formulas using these operations as deduction rules is implicationally sound and implicationally complete. In particular, if $f \in \overline{\text{QSAT}}$, then

$$\sum_{i=1}^s q_i p_i = 1 \quad (5.1)$$

for some $N \times N$ matrices q_1, q_2, \dots, q_s .

Example 4. Consider the uniform Ising model of n spins in one dimension, with a transverse magnetic field acting on the last spin. We can describe this system with the Hamiltonian

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} p_{i,i+1} + p_n \quad (5.2)$$

where

$$p_{i,j} = \frac{1 - (\sigma_z)_i (\sigma_z)_j}{2} \quad p_i = \frac{1 + (\sigma_x)_i}{2}$$

and the indices denote the spins on which act the Pauli matrices:

$$(\sigma_z)_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}_i \otimes 1 \quad (\sigma_x)_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}_i \otimes 1$$

We just shifted and rescaled the usual ‘X’ and ‘ZZ’ observables in order to make them projectors, with nullspaces coinciding with the ground spaces of the original observables. So we have

$$p_{i,j} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}_{i,j} \otimes 1 \quad p_i = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}_i \otimes 1$$

and the frustration of the Hamiltonian (5.2) is equivalent to

$$\{p_{1,2}, p_{2,3}, \dots, p_{n-1,n}, p_n\} \in \overline{\text{QSAT}}$$

Then, employing the deduction method explained above, we can prove that (5.2) is frustrated using the matrices

$$q_{n-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}_{n-1,n} \otimes 1 \quad q_n = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}_{n-1,n} \otimes 1$$

Indeed

$$q_{n-1} p_{n-1,n} + q_n p_n = 1$$

as one can verify operating only with 4×4 matrices on the last qubits:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

□

In this elementary example the contradiction is already created in the Hilbert space of just two qubits, and so the proof can be short, as the proving matrices are local. Locality, in our context, is a natural complexity measure. The connection of locality with the length is trivial: a k -local matrix can be expressed with $2^k \times 2^k$ entries. However note that, in the general case where n qubits are involved, even when all the matrices are local and so the (5.1) proof is short, we don't know how to verify it efficiently, because the different local spaces in general overlap, requiring us to expand the matrices in order to explicitly calculate all the operations¹¹.

To avoid this problem, the proof has to proceed "dynamically": by steps consisting of single matrix operations. In this way, if an operation increases the locality, that reflects in the dimensions of the resulting matrix, and the proof is efficiently verifiable with respect to its length¹². Let

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \underbrace{A}_{\mathcal{L}_a} \otimes 1 & b &= \underbrace{B}_{\mathcal{L}_b} \otimes 1 \\ &= \underbrace{A \otimes 1}_{\mathcal{L}_a \otimes \mathcal{L}_b} \otimes 1 & &= \underbrace{B \otimes 1}_{\mathcal{L}_a \otimes \mathcal{L}_b} \otimes 1 \\ &= \underbrace{A'}_{\mathcal{L}_a \otimes \mathcal{L}_b} \otimes 1 & &= \underbrace{B'}_{\mathcal{L}_a \otimes \mathcal{L}_b} \otimes 1 \end{aligned}$$

be two matrices of locality k_a, k_b , with $\mathcal{L}_a, \mathcal{L}_b$ of dimensions $2^{k_a}, 2^{k_b}$ respectively, then

$$\begin{aligned} a + b &= \underbrace{(A' + B')}_{\mathcal{L}_a \otimes \mathcal{L}_b} \otimes 1 & ab &= \underbrace{(A' B')}_{\mathcal{L}_a \otimes \mathcal{L}_b} \otimes 1 \end{aligned}$$

are in general of locality $k_a + k_b$. At the same time, it may even be that a step allows us to *reduce* locality¹³. To verify that the $2^{k_a+k_b} \times 2^{k_a+k_b}$ matrix c , resulting from an operation between a k_a -local matrix a and a k_b -local matrix b , is indeed k -local, with $k < k_a + k_b$, it is sufficient to reorder the $k_a + k_b$ qubits labels in such a way that c is expressed by just a $2^k \times 2^k$ block, repeated on the diagonal $2^{k_a+k_b-k}$ times: the verification can be done efficiently knowing the qubits on which the reduced matrix acts nontrivially.

Now let's precisely fix the above ideas in a definite system. We aim to perform actual operations only between matrices a, b that have the same local space: in this way the operation simply consists of direct addition or multiplication of their local matrices A, B , on their common space \mathcal{L} . We

¹¹If we allow a representation of the matrices as sums over different local spaces, expansion is unnecessary; we leverage this approach in the enhanced version of the proof system, in Section 6. For now, matrices and matrix operations are always expressed explicitly (albeit in sparse form) on definite local spaces, as described in Section 2.2.

¹²For analogous reasons, we need not be concerned about the possible growth of matrix entries' length throughout the derivation.

¹³Both addition and multiplication can happen to reduce the locality. For instance:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}_2 \otimes 1 \end{aligned}$$

allow this by the following ‘algebraic’ step rules:

$$\{(\underbrace{A}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes 1), (\underbrace{B}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes 1)\} \vdash (\underbrace{(A+B)}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes 1) \quad (\text{addition})$$

$$(\underbrace{A}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes 1) \vdash (\underbrace{(QA)}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes 1) \quad (\text{left multiplication})$$

where Q is any square matrix on the space \mathcal{L} . Furthermore, to make operations in this way between arbitrary matrices, we need beforehand to adequately expand their local spaces; and clearly it is essential to *reduce* them whenever it’s possible. Therefore we also allow the following ‘locality’ steps:

$$(\underbrace{P}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes 1) \vdash (\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} P & 0 \\ 0 & P \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathcal{L} \otimes \mathbb{C}_i^2} \otimes 1) \quad (\text{expansion})$$

$$(\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} P & 0 \\ 0 & P \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathcal{L} \otimes \mathbb{C}_i^2} \otimes 1) \vdash (\underbrace{P}_{\mathcal{L}} \otimes 1) \quad (\text{reduction})$$

for any qubit i not included in the register of \mathcal{L} .

To be thorough, let’s also explicitly address the special case of deriving a null matrix: in the Dirac notation used by the system, this is automatically reduced to the 0 scalar. In any case there is no need for a proof to derive the (always obtainable) null matrix: since adding or multiplying it does not yield any new matrix.

In conclusion, a MATRICIAL CALCULUS (MC) proof of locality k is a sequence of (at most) k -local matrices, expressed locally as described in Section 2.2; for each matrix of the sequence it is indicated how it is obtained from previous matrices and the initial ones by the application of one of the rules above.

In particular, the final matrix in a $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$ refutation will always be the 0-local scalar 1.

Example 5. Assume the proof has obtained, as in Example 4, the 2-local identity matrix on the space of two qubits i_1, i_2 . Then it can formally obtain the scalar 1 with two applications of the reduction rule, on qubits i_1, i_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}_{i_1, i_2} \otimes 1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}_{i_2} \otimes 1 \\ &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

□

Note that locality steps have no semantic effect, and are therefore trivially sound. Algebraic steps are sound for the trivial direction of Theorem 3. And the algebraic and expansion steps together are complete for the nontrivial direction of Theorem 3, since they allow for arbitrary additions and left-multiplications. Finally, note that each step is efficiently verifiable via deterministic classical computation.

Short derivations of 1 thus provide a convenient way to verify quantum unsatisfiability. However, in the general case, the proving matrices are n -local and a short proof does not exist (as expected, otherwise we would have $\overline{\text{QSAT}} \in \mathcal{NP}$). We will later prove this in the $\overline{\text{SAT}}$ subcase, by demonstrating the equivalence between MC and Resolution on classical instances.

5.1 Classical Subcase (DMC)

Let p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s be the diagonal projectors translating the Boolean formulas p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s as explained in Section 3.1. A trivial proof that p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s have no common satisfying assignment is just the addition $p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_s$: the resulting diagonal matrix must have full rank (then it can be formally multiplied by its inverse and reduced to 1). However to calculate $p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_s$ we have in general to expand the local p_i to their full matrices. The point of MC is that local manipulations can help keep the matrices small: an MC diagonal proof of locality d involves only matrices specified by (at most) 2^d entries of the diagonal. Note also that the essential information provided by the proof here is which matrices to consider and under which locality: to follow the proof semantically in the diagonal case we don't really need to perform matrix operations, since the nullspaces of diagonal matrices are directly evident.

Of course, there are matricial proofs of classical formulas in which appear non-diagonal matrices. However, *the use of non-diagonal matrices is always inessential in proofs of classical formulas*. In the static case, the argument is rather immediate: if p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s are diagonal matrices, then one obtains from (5.1) a diagonal proof just nullifying every non-diagonal entry of the q_i . However, repeated multiplications make non-diagonal elements relevant. In any case we will show that the restriction to diagonal matrices through the proof (we denote such a system by DMC) never requires increasing the locality of the matrices. The mapping, though, is less immediate in the dynamic case.

Theorem 6. *We can map any k -local MC proof of a classical formula to a k -local DMC proof of the same formula.*

Proof. We will map each matrix obtained by the MC proof to a diagonal matrix with the same locality. Let

$$p = [|\Psi_1\rangle \quad |\Psi_2\rangle \quad \dots \quad |\Psi_N\rangle]$$

be any matrix, considered as a row of column vectors $|\Psi_i\rangle$; we map p to the diagonal projector p' defined by the following diagonal entries:

$$(p')_{i,i} = \begin{cases} 0 & |\Psi_i\rangle = 0 \\ 1 & |\Psi_i\rangle \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

Observe that if

$$p = \begin{bmatrix} P & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & P & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & & & \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & P \end{bmatrix}$$

then

$$p' = \begin{bmatrix} P' & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & P' & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & & & \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & P' \end{bmatrix}$$

where P' is the diagonal (5.3) mapping of P (i.e., $(P')_{i,i}$ is either 0 or 1 depending on whether the i -th column of P is null or not). Thus p' has the same local space as p : we made a *local* transformation $P \mapsto P'$.

We will show by induction that, if we have the (5.3) mappings p'_1, p'_2, \dots, p'_s of some matrices p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s , we can obtain, using only diagonal matrices of locality k , the mapping of any matrix deducible from p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s with k -local steps. Thus, in particular, if there is a k -local refutation

$$\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\} \vdash 1$$

there is a k -local and diagonal refutation

$$\{p'_1, p'_2, \dots, p'_s\} \vdash 1$$

since

$$1' = 1$$

Then the theorem follows because, in the case of classical logic formulas, the initial matrices p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s coincide with their p'_1, p'_2, \dots, p'_s mappings¹⁴.

¹⁴In a more general case, if the initial diagonal matrices p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s are not projectors, we can straightforwardly

For locality steps, it is clear that the mapping of any expansion or reduction of $P \otimes 1$ is obtained by the corresponding expansion or reduction of $P' \otimes 1$. Let's thus consider, in the remainder of the proof, algebraic steps in a given local space \mathcal{L} .

Assume we obtained the mapping $A' \otimes 1$ of a matrix $A \otimes 1$, and let

$$C = Q A$$

for some matrix Q on \mathcal{L} . We can obtain the mapping $C' \otimes 1$ of $C \otimes 1$ with a diagonal matrix on the space \mathcal{L} . Indeed, left multiplication preserves null columns; so C has all the null columns that A , and A' , have, and possibly new ones; then we have

$$C' = C' A'$$

considering that the (5.3) matrices are diagonal matrices with Boolean values.

For the addition step, let's assume we obtained the mappings $A' \otimes 1, B' \otimes 1$ of two matrices $A \otimes 1, B \otimes 1$, and consider

$$S = A + B \tag{5.4}$$

Analogously to above, S' has all the null columns that are null in both A' and B' , which coincide with the null columns of $A' + B'$ (since the (5.3) matrices are non-negative). We can obtain the further columns that might cancel out in the sum (5.4), by multiplying both A', B' by S' and summing the results; we obtain in this way the diagonal matrix

$$D = S' A' + S' B'$$

with entries in $\{0, 1, 2\}$. The '2' entries are for those columns that are not null in each of A', B', S' , so we can normalize them by obtaining also $S' A' B'$ and subtracting it from D . Finally we have

$$S' = S' A' + S' B' - S' A' B'$$

Note that we can even have a projector at each step by first doing $S' A' - S' A' B'$, for example, and then adding the remaining matrix $S' B'$: so that '2' entries are always avoided. ■

Let's point out some additional observations about the construction in the proof of the theorem above. First of all, note that the DMC proof only requires a linear increase in length and number of steps with respect to the original MC proof. Moreover, note that we mapped the generic MC proof of a classical formula to a DMC proof in which appear *projectors* only; this is a key constraint that allows Resolution to simulate MC on CNF formulas, as we will readily see in the next section.

5.2 Equivalence Between DMC and R

Resolution proof system (R) deals with CNF formulas, i.e. sets of clauses. A clause

$$m = l_{i_1} \sqcup l_{i_2} \sqcup \dots \sqcup l_{i_k} \tag{5.5}$$

with k literals $l_{i_1}, l_{i_2}, \dots, l_{i_k}$, can be specified by the partial assignment P that falsifies it. So it is represented, as a quantum formula, by the projector onto that assignment:

$$m = |P\rangle\langle P| \otimes 1 \tag{5.6}$$

Note that expressing the clause by (5.5) or (5.6) requires essentially the same length (bit size), which grows linearly with k ; and both translations are computationally trivial.

Resolution traditionally has only one deduction rule:

$$\{a \sqcup x_i, b \sqcup \tilde{x}_i\} \vdash (a \sqcup b) \tag{resolution}$$

where x_i is a variable and a, b any clauses (including the empty clause). But it is folklore in proof complexity (you can find the easy proof in [13]) that, adding the rule

$$a \vdash (a \sqcup q) \tag{weakening}$$

where q is any clause, one obtains an equivalent system; so we can make use of the weakening rule, or ignore it, as it is of our best convenience.

In order to simulate a Resolution refutation with MC it suffices to represent clauses by projectors and implement the resolution rule using ideal operations and locality adjustments.

obtain p'_1, p'_2, \dots, p'_s through local multiplications. But, for *non-diagonal* initial matrices, the induction will generally lack the basis steps: we cannot in general obtain p' from p (for example we cannot infer 1 solely from the fact that p has no null columns, otherwise the system would not be sound).

Theorem 7. *DMC efficiently simulates R.*

Proof. In the diagonal case, all the matrices commute. Clauses, in particular, are diagonal *projectors*; and the projector c corresponding to the disjunction of two commuting projectors a, b is simply given by

$$c = ab$$

Let x_i, \tilde{x}_i be the matrices representing the one-literal clauses x_i, \tilde{x}_i respectively, then the premises of a resolution step are the matrices corresponding to certain products $ax_i, b\tilde{x}_i$; and the conclusion is the matrix corresponding to ab . We can derive the latter from the former ones according to

$$\begin{aligned} b(ax_i) + a(b\tilde{x}_i) &= ab(x_i + \tilde{x}_i) \\ &= ab \end{aligned} \tag{5.7}$$

This consists of two expansions, two multiplications, one addition and one reduction step. ■

In particular note that the width¹⁵ (w) in the R proof, corresponds to locality (k) in the MC simulation: rigorously we have

$$k = w + 1$$

because right before the simplification step in (5.7) the i -th qubit is still formally involved, albeit already void semantically. Number of steps and length of the proof increase at most linearly.

For the inverse simulation, we have seen in Section 5.1 that, in proofs of classical formulas, we can limit ourselves to diagonal matrices *with only 0, 1 entries*. That is, a generic k -local matrix here has the form

$$p = \sum_{j=1}^r |P_j\rangle\langle P_j| \otimes 1 \tag{5.8}$$

with

$$r \leq 2^k$$

Each non-null term $|P\rangle\langle P| \otimes 1$ in (5.8) corresponds to the clause m falsified by the P assignment of k bits. So that p corresponds to a set of r clauses $\{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_r\}$ of width k .

Theorem 8. *R efficiently simulates DMC.*

Proof. Consider the locality steps on page 14, for the operator (5.8). An expansion is simulated with two applications of the weakening rule for each clause p_j of p :

$$p_j \vdash (p_j \sqcup x_i) \qquad p_j \vdash (p_j \sqcup \tilde{x}_i)$$

A reduction is simulated with one application of the resolution rule for each clause p_j of p :

$$\{p_j \sqcup x_i, p_j \sqcup \tilde{x}_i\} \vdash p_j$$

We don't need to simulate algebraic steps because, in the special DMC proof that we are simulating (where each matrix is a diagonal *projector*), addition and multiplication rules merely correspond, respectively, to merging two sets of clauses and selectively eliminating clauses from a set. ■

Again, width matches locality. The length is not increased. And, for a k -local proof, the number of *steps* in the R simulation grows by a $\mathcal{O}(2^k)$ factor.

6 The Enhanced Proof System (MC+)

In MC+ we allow matrices to be expressed as sums of terms with *different* local spaces.

It will prove useful, in particular to readily compare our matricial system with polynomial ones, to introduce some custom notation and terminology. Let

$$x_i = (|1\rangle\langle 1|)_i \otimes 1 \qquad \tilde{x}_i = (|0\rangle\langle 0|)_i \otimes 1 \qquad \hat{x}_i = (|0\rangle\langle 1|)_i \otimes 1 \qquad \check{x}_i = (|1\rangle\langle 0|)_i \otimes 1 \tag{6.1}$$

We call these 1-local matrices, four for each qubit i , LITERAL OPERATORS. We also use the notations

$$\mathfrak{X}_i = \{x_i, \tilde{x}_i, \hat{x}_i, \check{x}_i\} \qquad \mathfrak{X} = \mathfrak{X}_1 \cup \mathfrak{X}_2 \cup \dots \cup \mathfrak{X}_n \tag{6.2}$$

¹⁵The maximum number of literals (of different variables) in a clause.

The k -local operators

$$m = l_{i_1} l_{i_2} \dots l_{i_k} \quad l_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k} \in \mathfrak{X} \quad (6.3)$$

obtained by multiplying literals of k qubits i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k , will be called MONOMIAL OPERATORS. Note that literals of different qubits commute with each other so their ordering in (6.3) is not relevant.

Now consider a non-zero entry $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ in the local matrix P of (2.3), with $x_{i_1} x_{i_2} \dots x_{i_k}$ and $x'_{i_1} x'_{i_2} \dots x'_{i_k}$ the labelings of its row and column respectively: as a term in the Dirac expression of P , the entry corresponds to the linear operator

$$\alpha |x_{i_1} x_{i_2} \dots x_{i_k}\rangle \langle x'_{i_1} x'_{i_2} \dots x'_{i_k}| = \alpha (|x_{i_1}\rangle \langle x'_{i_1}| \otimes 1) (|x_{i_2}\rangle \langle x'_{i_2}| \otimes 1) \dots (|x_{i_k}\rangle \langle x'_{i_k}| \otimes 1)$$

Then the k -local operator (2.4) is equivalently rewritten as a linear combination of ‘monomial operators’ of the form (6.3), each acting on the same local space \mathcal{L} . If we let the monomials involve different sets of qubits (including the empty set: i.e. scalars, which we interpret as constant diagonal matrices), we have a more versatile way of expressing matrices than was possible in MC. In particular, since

$$x_i + \tilde{x}_i = 1 \quad \forall i \quad (6.4)$$

we can always express one of the operators $x_i, \tilde{x}_i, 1$ in terms of the other two, combining 0-local and 1-local matrices.

Example 9. Consider the 2-local matrix

$$p = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}_{x,y} \otimes 1 \quad (6.5)$$

acting nontrivially on the space of the x, y qubits respectively. In MC it is expressed as the sum

$$p = (|00\rangle\langle 01| + |10\rangle\langle 10| + |10\rangle\langle 11| + |11\rangle\langle 11|) \otimes 1$$

Or

$$p = \tilde{x} \hat{y} + x \tilde{y} + x \hat{y} + x y$$

using the notation (6.1) (with different letters instead of indices, to improve readability).

But, since (6.4), it is also

$$\begin{aligned} p &= (\tilde{x} + x) \hat{y} + x (\tilde{y} + y) \\ &= \hat{y} + x \end{aligned}$$

I.e. we can write the 2-local matrix p as a sum of 1-local terms acting separately on the x, y qubits. \square

Note that, regardless of expansions and reductions, the representation of a matrix in this form is not unique. Given a certain matrix expression p , we call DEGREE of p the maximum locality of its terms, and denote it by $\text{deg}(p)$. Should we explicitly make the sum of, say, n matrices of locality 1, we would have in general a matrix of locality n : a $2^n \times 2^n$ matrix versus n matrices 2×2 ; the sum grows linearly with n , while the resulting matrix grows *exponentially*. We will later show that this gives to our matricial system an actual strengthening: equivalent to the separation between Resolution (R) and Polynomial Calculus with Resolution (PCR) in the classical subcase [5].

Arithmetic operations between matrices expressed in the MC+ way can be done straightforwardly. Addition of any two matrices a, b is just given by the sum of the terms of both a and b , with terms on the same set of literals added together in a single term. Multiplication is done applying the distributive property and 1-local matrix products between literals on the same qubit¹⁶,

¹⁶Which obey the following algebra:

$$\begin{array}{llll} x^2 = x & \tilde{x}x = 0 & \hat{x}x = \hat{x} & \check{x}x = 0 \\ x\tilde{x} = 0 & \tilde{x}^2 = \tilde{x} & \hat{x}\tilde{x} = 0 & \check{x}\tilde{x} = \check{x} \\ x\hat{x} = 0 & \tilde{x}\hat{x} = \hat{x} & \hat{x}^2 = 0 & \check{x}\hat{x} = x \\ x\check{x} = \check{x} & \tilde{x}\check{x} = 0 & \hat{x}\check{x} = \tilde{x} & \check{x}^2 = 0 \end{array}$$

while we leave the (commutative) products of scalars and literals on different qubits expressed as multilinear terms.

Example 10. Let

$$a = \tilde{x}\hat{y} + y - \hat{y} \qquad b = \hat{y} + 2$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} a + b &= (\tilde{x}\hat{y} + y - \hat{y}) + (\hat{y} + 2) & ab &= \tilde{x}\hat{y}\hat{y} + 2\tilde{x}\hat{y} + y\hat{y} + 2y - \hat{y}^2 - 2\hat{y} \\ &= \tilde{x}\hat{y} + y + 2 & &= \tilde{x}y + 2\tilde{x}\hat{y} + 2y - 2\hat{y} \end{aligned}$$

□

I.e. additions and multiplications can be performed directly, without requiring a prior expansion of the matrices to a common local space.

Therefore we recast the algebraic step rules without imposing any restriction on the local space of the matrices:

$$\begin{aligned} \{a, b\} \vdash (a + b) & \qquad \text{(addition)} \\ a \vdash qa & \qquad \text{(left multiplication)} \end{aligned}$$

where q is any matrix and a, b are either previously derived matrices or initial ones. Expansion steps are thus not needed, and can be in any case simulated multiplying by $x_i + \tilde{x}_i$. As for reduction steps, it is convenient here to generalize them with the introduction of the following

$$\vdash w_i \qquad \forall i \qquad \text{(axioms)}$$

with

$$w_i = 1 - x_i - \tilde{x}_i$$

All the matricial expressions w_i correspond to the 0 scalar operator (and thus they are trivially sound), but they allow us to readily simulate reduction steps:

$$\begin{aligned} (px_i + p\tilde{x}_i) &\vdash \{(px_i + p\tilde{x}_i), (1 - x_i - \tilde{x}_i)\} \\ &\vdash \{(px_i + p\tilde{x}_i), (p - px_i - p\tilde{x}_i)\} \\ &\vdash p \end{aligned}$$

and, more generally, to move between different expressions of the same matrix.

It is straightforward to see that the proof system MC+ defined by the matrix representation and the deduction rules described above is sound and efficiently verifiable. Moreover, MC+ clearly generalizes the MC proof system presented in Section 5: any MC proof can essentially be seen as an MC+ proof where the matrices are kept expressed individually in terms of a single local matrix (as in (2.3)). We will see in the course of the next two subsections that, when applied to classical formulas, MC+ is equivalent to PCR; therefore its power strictly exceeds that of MC.

6.1 Classical Subcase (DMC+)

Here, we want to study the power of MC+ on diagonal instances, under the constraint that only diagonal matrices are used throughout the entire proof (we denote such a restricted system by DMC+). Since MC and MC+ essentially differ only for the representation of the matrices, we already know from Section 5.1 that DMC+ is complete, on diagonal instances, and simulates on them both MC and MC+ for the overall locality of the matrices. In MC+, however, some matrices of high locality can be efficiently represented as sums of matrices of lower locality. So a better complexity parameter for MC+ is the degree. We define the DEGREE of an MC+ proof as the maximum degree of its matrix expressions, i.e. the maximum locality of their individual terms. If the locality of the derivation is k , we have degree $\leq k$.

We will prove in this section that DMC+ is equivalent to MC+ on diagonal instances; in particular the restriction to diagonal matrices never requires a penalty on the degree of the proof. The mapping idea used in the proof of Theorem 6 doesn't work here: if we "diagonalize" each term of a sum $\sum \alpha_i m_i$ with the (5.3) mapping, we lose soundness because some null column of the sum could be not null in $\sum \alpha_i m'_i$. We will need here to diagonalize separately on each variable, with a different set up. Our mapping, in turn, will be less tight than in Theorem 6, as the diagonal matrices we will obtain aren't in general projectors. To better describe our diagonalization we first introduce some convenient concepts and notation.

Given any matrix expression p , and any qubit x , we have

$$p = p_0 + p_1 x + p_2 \tilde{x} + p_3 \hat{x} + p_4 \check{x}$$

for some matrix expressions p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 that do not involve the x qubit. We say that p is DIAGONAL with respect to x iff $p_3, p_4 = 0$. We call the set

$$D_x(p) = \{\mathbf{d}_x(p), \mathbf{d}'_x(p)\} \quad (6.6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{d}_x(p) = p_0 + p_1 x + p_2 \tilde{x} \qquad \mathbf{d}'_x(p) = p_3 x + p_4 \tilde{x}$$

the DIAGONALIZATION of p with respect to x ; we refer to $\mathbf{d}_x(p)$ and $\mathbf{d}'_x(p)$ as the DIAGONAL and ANTIDIAGONAL components, respectively, of the diagonalization $D_x(p)$. Note that

$$D_x(p) \vdash p$$

since

$$p = \mathbf{d}_x(p) + (\hat{x} + \check{x}) \mathbf{d}'_x(p)$$

So $D_x(p)$ provides a way to keep the whole semantic information of p in two matrix expressions that are diagonal with respect to x , and whose locality and degree are no greater than those of p . The length of $D_x(p)$ is the same as that of p , because every term appearing in one also appears in the other, up to possible interchanges between x, \hat{x} and between \tilde{x}, \check{x} . Of course in general p and $D_x(p)$ are not equivalent:

$$p \not\vdash D_x(p)$$

But, from a set f of diagonal matrices, for every matrix p such that $f \vdash p$, we can obtain both $\mathbf{d}_x(p)$ and $\mathbf{d}'_x(p)$, with a derivation in which every matrix is diagonal with respect to x .

Indeed, let say that a derivation $f \vdash d$ is DIAGONAL with respect to the x qubit iff every matrix occurring in it is diagonal with respect to x , and write this as $f \vdash_x d$. Then we can readily states the following two elementary lemmas.

Lemma 11.

$$\{D_x(a), D_x(b)\} \vdash_x D_x(a + b)$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} c &= a + b \\ &= (a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 \tilde{x} + a_3 \hat{x} + a_4 \check{x}) + (b_0 + b_1 x + b_2 \tilde{x} + b_3 \hat{x} + b_4 \check{x}) \\ &= (a_0 + b_0) + (a_1 + b_1)x + (a_2 + b_2)\tilde{x} + (a_3 + b_3)\hat{x} + (a_4 + b_4)\check{x} \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\mathbf{d}_x(c) = (a_0 + b_0) + (a_1 + b_1)x + (a_2 + b_2)\tilde{x}$$

and

$$\mathbf{d}'_x(c) = (a_3 + b_3)x + (a_4 + b_4)\tilde{x}$$

That can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}_x(c) &= \mathbf{d}_x(a) + \mathbf{d}_x(b) \\ &= (a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 \tilde{x}) + (b_0 + b_1 x + b_2 \tilde{x}) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}'_x(c) &= \mathbf{d}'_x(a) + \mathbf{d}'_x(b) \\ &= (a_3x + a_4\tilde{x}) + (b_3x + b_4\tilde{x}) \end{aligned}$$

■

Lemma 12.

$$D_x(a) \vdash_x D_x(ba) \quad \forall b$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} c &= ba \\ &= (b_0 + b_1x + b_2\tilde{x} + b_3\hat{x} + b_4\tilde{\tilde{x}})(a_0 + a_1x + a_2\tilde{x} + a_3\hat{x} + a_4\tilde{\tilde{x}}) \\ &= b_0a_0 + (b_0a_1 + b_1a_0 + b_1a_1 + b_4a_3)x + (b_0a_2 + b_2a_0 + b_2a_2 + b_3a_4)\tilde{x} \\ &\quad + (b_0a_3 + b_2a_3 + b_3a_0 + b_3a_1)\hat{x} + (b_0a_4 + b_1a_4 + b_4a_0 + b_4a_2)\tilde{\tilde{x}} \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\mathbf{d}_x(c) = b_0a_0 + (b_0a_1 + b_1a_0 + b_1a_1 + b_4a_3)x + (b_0a_2 + b_2a_0 + b_2a_2 + b_3a_4)\tilde{x}$$

and

$$\mathbf{d}'_x(c) = (b_0a_3 + b_2a_3 + b_3a_0 + b_3a_1)x + (b_0a_4 + b_1a_4 + b_4a_0 + b_4a_2)\tilde{\tilde{x}}$$

That can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}_x(c) &= (b_0 + b_1x + b_2\tilde{x})\mathbf{d}_x(a) + (b_4x + b_3\tilde{x})\mathbf{d}'_x(a) \\ &= (b_0 + b_1x + b_2\tilde{x})(a_0 + a_1x + a_2\tilde{x}) + (b_4x + b_3\tilde{x})(a_3x + a_4\tilde{\tilde{x}}) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}'_x(c) &= (b_0 + b_2x + b_1\tilde{x})\mathbf{d}'_x(a) + (b_3x + b_4\tilde{x})\mathbf{d}_x(a) \\ &= (b_0 + b_2x + b_1\tilde{x})(a_3x + a_4\tilde{\tilde{x}}) + (b_3x + b_4\tilde{x})(a_0 + a_1x + a_2\tilde{x}) \end{aligned}$$

■

Now consider any derivation $f \vdash d$ in which the premised matrices f and the deduced matrix d are all diagonal, but the intermediate steps involve non-diagonal matrices. Being the f matrices diagonal they are equivalent to their diagonalization sets (6.6) (the diagonal component coincides with the matrix and the antidiagonal one is null); then we can by induction, as shown by lemmas 11 and 12, obtain the diagonalizations of all subsequent matrices in the derivation. Being the final matrix also diagonal, in this way we obtain it with a derivation $f \vdash_x d$ all diagonal in the x qubit. The important property of this simulation, defined by the induction steps described in the proof of the lemmas above, is that the degree of $f \vdash_x d$ is the same as that of the original derivation $f \vdash d$: because, up to interchanges of literals of the x qubit, every term appearing in the simulation also appears in the original derivation. For the same reason, even the length is the same (noticing that the simulation steps take care of every original term only once). However the number of steps is generally doubled¹⁷: indeed for every matrix p obtained in the original derivation, the simulation has to obtain the two matrices in $D_x(p)$. This means that, repeating the diagonalization for every qubit in the k -local space of p , we would need to derive 2^k different matrices. This would give to the full diagonal simulation of a general k -local proof a trivial 2^k factor in the number of steps. This is unnecessary in many cases, since most of the matrices of the diagonalization would be null.

To see this, and refine our simulation, let's extend the diagonalization (6.6) to a set of matrices:

$$D_x(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_l) = D_x(p_1) \cup D_x(p_2) \cup \dots \cup D_x(p_l)$$

and a set of qubits:

$$D_{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k}(p) = D_{x_1}(D_{x_2}(\dots D_{x_k}(p)))$$

and let $D(p)$ denote the diagonalization of p with respect to all the qubits in its local space. Each of the 2^k matrices in $D(p)$ correspond to the selection of a component, diagonal or antidiagonal, for

¹⁷More precisely, it is doubled for addition steps and increases sixfold for multiplication steps (which require two multiplications and one addition for each component in the diagonal simulation).

each qubit. But each term of p has, with respect to each qubit, just the diagonal or the antidiagonal component, so each term contributes to only one matrix in $D(p)$, so the number of non-null matrices in $D(p)$ cannot be more than the number r of terms in p . Then for each p in the non-diagonal proof, we need only to deduce r diagonal matrices in the diagonal simulation, each of which requires $\mathcal{O}(k)$ steps. So if R is the total number of terms across all matrices in the original k -local proof, the number of steps required by the diagonal simulation is $\mathcal{O}(kR)$; or, more loosely, $\mathcal{O}(kl)$, where l is the length (bit size) of the original proof.

We summarize the results of the present section in the following theorem.

Theorem 13. *Let $f \vdash d$ be an MC+ derivation between diagonal matrices, with locality, degree and length respectively k, g, l . It is possible to construct a DMC+ derivation $f \vdash d$ with locality, degree, length and number of steps respectively $k, g, \mathcal{O}(l), \mathcal{O}(kl)$.* ■

6.2 Equivalence Between DMC+ and PCR

As we have seen in Section 5 that MC is equivalent to Resolution on the instances where both systems apply (i.e. sets of diagonal projectors or CNF formulas), we will now see that the same result holds between MC+ and PCR. For the coefficients in both systems we consider a common, generic field \mathbb{F} .

First, let us recall the definition of PCR, as it results from the classical textbook [29]. Given an instance set

$$f = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$$

of polynomials $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s \in \mathbb{F}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, \bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_n]$ in the independent variables x_i, \bar{x}_i , and three sets of axioms:

$$\vdash u_i \qquad \vdash v_i \qquad \vdash w_i \qquad \forall i$$

with

$$u_i = x_i^2 - x_i \qquad v_i = \bar{x}_i^2 - \bar{x}_i \qquad w_i = 1 - x_i - \bar{x}_i$$

PCR deduces new polynomials by the rules

$$\{a, b\} \vdash (a + b) \qquad \text{(addition)}$$

$$a \vdash qa \qquad \text{(multiplication)}$$

where $q \in \mathbb{F}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, \bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_n]$ is any polynomial and a, b are previously derived polynomials or initial ones.

Given a polynomial p , we map it to the diagonal matrix expression p (we use respectively roman and italic fonts to distinguish the two) obtained operating in p the substitutions

$$x_i \mapsto \mathbf{x}_i \qquad \bar{x}_i \mapsto \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i$$

of the variables x_i, \bar{x}_i with the operators $\mathbf{x}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i$ defined in (6.1); interpreting the algebraic operations, addition and (commutative) multiplication, as the corresponding operations between diagonal matrices. It is readily seen from the definition of $\mathbf{x}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i$ that, for any assignment X , we have

$$\mathbf{x}_i |X\rangle = x_i |X\rangle \qquad \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i |X\rangle = (1 - x_i) |X\rangle \qquad (6.7)$$

where x_i is the value of the i -th bit in assignment X . Then, by induction on the construction of the formula we obtain

$$p |X\rangle = p(X) |X\rangle$$

where $p(X)$ is the value of p on the assignment X for x_i variables and the complementary assignment for \bar{x}_i variables (so that $\bar{x}_1 = 1 - x_1, \bar{x}_2 = 1 - x_2, \dots, \bar{x}_n = 1 - x_n$). The nullspace of p is thus spanned by the Boolean assignments $|X\rangle$ such that $p(X) = 0$. This implies that we can trivially translate

any polynomial proof into a matricial proof, and thus we have the following theorem.

Theorem 14. *DMC+ efficiently simulates PCR.*

Proof. The initial polynomials translate into the same expressions in terms of the diagonal operators x_i, \tilde{x}_i . The axioms either transform to the null matrix, or to the (diagonal) w_i axioms of MC+.

Addition and multiplication steps in the polynomial proof can be simulated matricially by the same operations between the same expressions in terms of the operators x_i, \tilde{x}_i , in place of the variables x_i, \bar{x}_i . The (commutative) algebra is formally the same in both cases, except that in MC+ all powers x_i^a, \tilde{x}_i^a are automatically reduced to x_i, \tilde{x}_i for every $a \geq 2$. The matrices obtained are the matricial mappings of the polynomials obtained in the polynomial proof. In particular the matricial mapping of the constant 1 polynomial, is the 1 operator. ■

The DMC+ simulation just mirrors the original PCR proof, except that all the linearization steps are redundant in DMC+: they become deductions of 0 and additions of it to previously obtained matrices.

Since the polynomial to matrix mapping is not sensible to the degree of the single variables, because x_i, x_i^2 map to the same operator x_i , it is not injective. However for the reverse mapping we can consider only multilinear polynomials. So, given a matrix expression p , let p be the polynomial obtained operating in p the substitutions

$$x_i \mapsto x_i \qquad \tilde{x}_i \mapsto \bar{x}_i$$

Using the (6.7) as above we can readily see that

$$p(X) = \langle X | p | X \rangle$$

And it's clear that the matrix translation of a multilinear polynomial p coincides with the matrix p of which p is the polynomial translation. In other words we have a bijection between diagonal matrices and multilinear polynomials. As a consequence we can essentially map a diagonal matricial proof to a polynomial proof by just translating the matrices in the corresponding polynomials.

Theorem 15. *PCR efficiently simulates DMC+.*

Proof. The only difference we have with PCR is that in a DMC+ proof the terms are always linear: because multiplying literals on the same qubit does not increase the degree. Anyway we can, in the PCR simulation of a DMC+ proof, just keep the corresponding polynomials linearized after each multiplication, using the u_i, v_i axioms. Clearly, the linearization of a polynomial p can be done in $\mathcal{O}(|p|)$ steps, each of length $\mathcal{O}(|p|)$ and degree not greater than that of p . ■

7 Proof Search Algorithm

Constant-degree polynomial proofs can be efficiently found (i.e. in time polynomial with respect to their minimum length) [14]; and so DMC+ proofs, based on what we have seen in Section 6.2. As an example of the many classical results that it is possible to extend to the general quantum case, in this section we adapt the proof search algorithm¹⁸ in [14] to any MC+ proof. In particular, if constant-degree proofs exist for a family of growing QSAT formulas, they can be found by a classical algorithm within a polynomial number of bounded-precision operations (as long as the coefficients of the proving matrices do not overflow the precision bound).

Given a set of initial matrices $f = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$ and a positive integer d , we will use here the notation $f \vdash_d p$ to denote that the matrix p can be deduced from f with an MC+ derivation of degree at most d ; we have of course

$$d \geq \max(\deg(p_1), \deg(p_2), \dots, \deg(p_s), \deg(p))$$

¹⁸Two distinct but similar algorithms are proposed in [14], we here generalize the first one, which has a better worst-case bound.

We consider the set of matrix expressions

$$V_d(f) = \{p : f \vdash_d p\}$$

Note that $V_d(f)$ is a vector space:

$$(a \in V_d(f)) \wedge (b \in V_d(f)) \Rightarrow ((\alpha a + \beta b) \in V_d(f)) \quad \forall \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{F}$$

containing the axioms:

$$w_i \in V_d(f) \quad \forall i$$

and the initial matrices:

$$f \subseteq V_d(f)$$

Denoting by \mathfrak{X} the set of all literal operators, defined in (6.2), note that

$$(p \in V_d(f)) \wedge (\deg(xp) \leq d) \Rightarrow (xp \in V_d(f)) \quad \forall x \in \mathfrak{X}$$

In order to describe an algorithm that efficiently finds a proof of constant degree, we consider a total order relation \prec over the terms in matrix expressions, such that

$$(\deg(p) < \deg(p')) \Rightarrow (p \prec p')$$

Given a matrix expression

$$p \neq 0$$

let's denote by $\text{LT}(p)$ the largest term of p with respect to the order \prec (taken with its coefficient), and by $\text{LC}(p)$ its coefficient; and let

$$\text{LM}(p) = \frac{\text{LT}(p)}{\text{LC}(p)}$$

Example 16. Let's choose lexicographic order between terms of the same degree, with the following ordering among literals on the same qubit:

$$\tilde{x}_i \prec \hat{x}_i \prec \tilde{x}_i \prec x_i$$

Then for the matrix

$$p = 2x_1 \hat{x} + 3\tilde{x}_1 x_2 - \tilde{x}_1 + 7$$

we have

$$\text{LT}(p) = 2x_1 \hat{x}$$

$$\text{LC}(p) = 2$$

$$\text{LM}(p) = x_1 \hat{x}$$

□

Let's note that a matrix expression of degree d can have at most

$$\begin{aligned} N_d &= \sum_{g=0}^d 4^g \binom{n}{g} \\ &= \mathcal{O}((4n)^d) \end{aligned}$$

terms.

Let us now consider the set B of matrices returned by the pseudo-algorithm below. In any moment it is

$$\deg(b) \leq d \quad \forall b \in B \quad (7.1)$$

and

$$(b \neq b') \Rightarrow (\text{LM}(b) \neq \text{LM}(b')) \quad \forall b, b' \in B \quad (7.2)$$

Which requires that

$$|B| \leq N_d$$

Since every time that the algorithm adds matrices to be reduced, (at most $4n$ matrices,) in the previous block it just added a matrix to B , then

$$|A| \leq s + n + 4n N_d$$

The reduction of one matrix can proceed for at most N_d iterations, so the algorithm terminates in

Algorithm 1

```

A = [p1, p2, ..., ps, w1, w2, ..., wn] ..... /*matrices to be reduced*/
B = [] ..... /*basis*/
for p in A .....
  for b in B ..... /*reduction*/
    if LM(p) == LM(b) .....
      p = p -  $\frac{LC(p)}{LC(b)}$  b .....
    if p ≠ 0 .....
      B.append(p) ..... /*add to the basis*/
      for x in  $\mathfrak{X}$  .....
        if deg(xp) ≤ d .....
          A.append(xp) ..... /*add to matrices to be reduced*/
return B .....

```

a finite number T of steps. Precisely

$$\begin{aligned}
T &= \mathcal{O}(|A|(|B|N_d + 4n)) \\
&= \mathcal{O}(s(4n)^{2d}) + \mathcal{O}((4n)^{3d+1})
\end{aligned} \tag{7.3}$$

so it is polynomial for constant-degree proofs¹⁹.

Theorem 17. B is a basis of $V_d(f)$.

Proof. Let V be the vector space generated by the matrices in B . It is clear that

$$V \subseteq V_d(f)$$

because the steps of Algorithm 1 construct proofs of degree $\leq d$ for every matrix in B , starting from the matrices in f .

For the other direction, consider a

$$p \in V_d(f)$$

and let us prove that

$$p \in V \tag{7.4}$$

The space generated by the matrices in $A \cup B$ can only increase during the algorithm; because the reduction of a matrix p with respect to a set of matrices B doesn't change the span of $\{p\} \cup B$, and the algorithm either add new matrices to $A \cup B$, or reduces a matrix in A with respect to B . Then we have

$$f \subseteq V$$

and

$$w_i \in V \quad \forall i$$

Now take a derivation $f \vdash_d p$ and decompose it in way that multiplication steps only multiply by scalars $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}$ or literals $x \in \mathfrak{X}$. Addition steps and multiplications by scalars clearly leave the matrices in V . To prove (7.4) by induction, it thus only remains to consider the following case:

$$b' = xb \quad x \in \mathfrak{X}$$

where

$$b' \in V_d(f) \tag{7.5}$$

and

$$b \in V$$

¹⁹Note that, unless the field \mathbb{F} is finite, repeated divisions could make the coefficients uncontrollably grow, and then the true computational cost of “one step” of the algorithm could be superlinear. The issue concerns the original PC search algorithm as well as our generalization. To address this rigorously one would need to refine the algorithm with division-free techniques of reduction [39]. However, the original algorithm is commonly regarded as “efficient” in the literature of proof complexity, and one usually says that “constant degree PC is automatizable” (see [19] as one example).

We have

$$b = \sum_{j=1}^{|B|} \alpha_j b_j$$

for some

$$\alpha_j \in \mathbb{F} \qquad b_j \in B \qquad \forall j$$

And

$$b' = \sum_{j=1}^{|B|} \alpha_j x b_j \tag{7.6}$$

For (7.5) it must be

$$\deg(b') \leq d \tag{7.7}$$

Now let's claim

$$\deg(xb_j) \leq d \qquad \forall j \tag{7.8}$$

then for each b_j the algorithm added to the span of $A \cup B$, and so also to V , even xb_j . And thus

$$b' \in V$$

So we just miss to prove (7.8). Let's assume for absurd that (7.8) doesn't hold, for a set

$$J \neq \emptyset$$

of indices. Then

$$\deg(b_j) = d \qquad \forall j \in J \tag{7.9}$$

since in any case (7.1), and

$$\deg(xb_j) = d + 1 \qquad \forall j \in J \tag{7.10}$$

From (7.9) and (7.10) we deduce that $LT(b_j)$ doesn't contain the qubit of x (multiplications on the same qubit do not increase the degree). Then

$$LT(xb_j) = xLT(b_j) \qquad \forall j \in J \tag{7.11}$$

To have (7.6) and (7.7), the $LT(xb_j)$ for $j \in J$ must cancel out, because they have degree $d + 1$. This in particular requires

$$|J| \geq 2$$

And since we have always (7.2), we have

$$(j_1 \neq j_2) \Rightarrow (LM(xb_{j_1}) \neq LM(xb_{j_2})) \qquad \forall j_1, j_2 \in J$$

considering (7.11). But then the $LT(xb_j)$ cannot cancel out. ■

Now let us analyze more closely the reduction process in Algorithm 1. It is clear that if the reduction of a matrix p with respect to a set of matrices B gives the null matrix expression 0 , then p is a linear combination of the matrices in B . Keeping track of the reduction passages we form a proof $B \vdash_d p$ in less than N_d iterations; then keeping together also the proofs $f \vdash_d B$ already produced by Algorithm 1 we obtain a proof $f \vdash_d p$ in time (7.3). This method is thus sound, and efficient for constant d . And it is also complete, because the matrix p' obtained reducing p with B is such that $\{p\} \cup B$ and $\{p'\} \cup B$ form the same vector space, and

$$LM(p') \neq LM(b_j) \qquad \forall j$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} p' \neq 0 &\Rightarrow p' \notin V_d(f) \\ &\Rightarrow p \notin V_d(f) \end{aligned}$$

and contrapositively

$$p \in V_d(f) \Rightarrow p' = 0$$

8 Pudlák's Quantum Frege System

To the best of our knowledge, the only work in literature about quantum proof systems in proof complexity is a 2009 paper [33] by Pudlák. It specifically deals with two somewhat distinct topics.

One topic concerns the use of quantum mechanics to help *find* proofs (in propositional classical

logic). As noted in the introduction, we don't know how to use quantum mechanics to reduce the length of efficiently verifiable proofs in this context, but we know how to use quantum mechanics to perform certain computations (apparently) faster than any classical algorithm. For example we know how to factor integers efficiently with a quantum computer [37]. If a proof system can efficiently express factorization (or any one-way function), then polynomial-length proofs cannot in general be found efficiently with classical TMs, under well-established cryptographic assumptions. But it could be possible using quantum computation, if quantum computation can invert the one-way function. Pudlák shows two examples of Frege proofs that can be efficiently found only using quantum computers, if classical computers cannot factorize efficiently²⁰. He relies on the constructions of Frege encodings of bounded arithmetic relations developed in [10] and [12].

However the part of Pudlák's paper we aim to informally review here is his concept of "quantum proofs". In quantum complexity literature a quantum proof is typically considered as a quantum superposition of strings, to be verified by a quantum computation. Pudlák proposed a different notion of quantum proof (in classical logic), based on quantum manipulations of superpositions of Boolean formulas.

8.1 Quantum Rules

In [33], Pudlák introduces the notion of a QUANTUM DEDUCTION RULE: a unitary transformation R , acting on the span of a basis of vectors, where each basis vector $|S_i\rangle$ represents a sequence S_i of Boolean formulas, such that

$$(\langle S_j | R | S_i \rangle \neq 0) \Rightarrow (S_i \models S_j) \tag{8.1}$$

The application of a deduction rule is typically viewed as a step in a proof, whose correctness is to be verified by a computation. If we regard the deduction itself as a computational step, instead, then quantum deduction rules arise as a natural generalization of classical deduction rules, here understood as steps in a quantum computation. As such, we require them to be unitary; and (8.1) just expresses implicational soundness.

We want to apply a quantum deduction rule R to different instances of the formula schemes it refers to, just as we do with classical deduction rules. This can be achieved by applying R locally as a quantum gate, in the overall space \mathcal{S} generated by all the sequences of formulas (say of m formulas, in n variables, up to a length l). This just conveys the core idea, while the technical complications need not be described here.

We thus view a QUANTUM FREGE proof as a quantum circuit on the space \mathcal{S} starting from an initialized state and producing new superpositions of sets of formulas at each application of a rule gate. Since in this setting we do not retain memory of previous deduction steps, we have to maintain a sufficient number of formulas, in general much more than those involved in single deduction rules.

It's clear that any classical Frege proof can be transformed into a quantum Frege proof with the same number of steps. Classical deduction rules are represented in this case by permutation gates, so at each step we are in a basis state of \mathcal{S} : i.e. we have just a sequence of m formulas. These

²⁰Although both examples are not entirely cogent. In one case (the second presented by the paper, involving a metamathematical argument) proving the proposed tautologies may not require factorization, although no alternative proof strategy comes to mind and Pudlák conjectures that one cannot efficiently find Frege proofs of these tautologies without also being able to factorize efficiently. In the other example (based on Diffie-Hellman key exchange) there is not, strictly speaking, a family of tautologies for which to seek short Frege proofs; rather there is a family of *pairs* of formulas, where exactly one formula in each pair is a tautology; and what breaks the cryptography is already this decision, not constructing a proof of the tautology.

represent, at each step, the lines that we keep in a “blackboard proof”: where, for limited space, we are allowed to overwrite those that we don’t further need.

It is also clear that any formula that appears in superposition in a quantum Frege proof, can be obtained by a classical Frege proof in the same number of steps: there exists a computational path that connects it with the initial state, and each step can be obtained with the application of a corresponding classical deduction rule.

So Pudlák’s idea does not help in shortening proofs; although, a single proof can work for multiple tautologies: all those that appear (with a detectable amplitude) in the final superposition. Essentially, the whole sequence of superposition states, produced by successive applications of quantum deduction rules, could be described as a static superposition of classical Frege proofs of the same length. A similar idea may be applied to any other classical proof system.

8.2 Discussion

We argue that Pudlák’s idea does not capture an effective exemplification of the power of quantum proof systems. To clarify this point, let us frame Pudlák’s quantum proofs within the general notion of *certificates*, as understood in the context of computational complexity theory.

We can start by observing that Pudlák’s proofs are naturally encoded by classical certificates. Such a certificate, for a tautology f , is simply a string ξ specifying the quantum computation that corresponds to the sequence of quantum deduction rules intended to produce f . A classical TM can only check ξ by verifying that each applied rule is sound; but it cannot perform the computation to verify that it actually produces f . However we can give ξ , say, to a universal QTM, which, by executing the specified sequence of quantum deduction rules, reaches the final state and verifies the presence of f with a measurement. There is no obvious way to usefully encode Pudlák’s quantum proofs as quantum states; and if there was, it would encompass classical Frege proofs as well, since these can be represented as quantum Frege proofs.

But the problem with Pudlák’s idea, that makes it not usefully “quantum”, does not *per se* lie in its reliance on classical certificates; rather, this limitation critically combines with a more fundamental issue. Pudlák’s quantum proofs are quantum circuits, which we interpret as superposition of Frege proofs. Each quantum Frege proof, contains a classical Frege proof within the same number of steps. The power of quantum computation manifests in enhancing the output probabilities of certain computational paths (as well illustrated, for example, in the introductory textbook [23]); but in a verification setting, if one neither leverages quantum-state certificates nor permits any computational path to be unsound, the right path choice could simply be given by the certificate. In order to be sure that the quantum power is relevant, we have to use it not at the level of the logical steps in the proof, but at the level of the computational steps in the verification. In this sense, we can say that Pudlák’s quantum proofs capture the power of quantum computation, but fail to capture the power of *quantum verification*; that is, the power of quantum proof systems²¹.

²¹Although Pudlák shows that, under cryptographic assumptions, a classical computer cannot find efficiently certain Frege proofs, but it can find (the specification of) corresponding quantum Frege proofs. Moreover he conjectures that, given a quantum Frege proof, not even quantum computers can feasibly extract a classical Frege proof: this would give us tautologies for which only quantum proofs are available in practice. If it were not for the underlying structure of Frege systems, which in principle could be exploited in some way, the conjecture would be equivalent to the conjecture that it is infeasible, even for quantum computers, to extract, from a quantum computation, a classical path with nonzero amplitude (required for $BQP \not\subseteq NP$).

9 Quantum Systems for Quantum Unsatisfiability

Let us start from the following well-known result from basic complexity theory, which is a straightforward corollary of the Cook–Levin theorem.

Theorem 18.

$$(\overline{\text{SAT}} \in \mathcal{P}) \Leftrightarrow (\text{co}\mathcal{NP} = \mathcal{P})$$

■

Theorem 18 can clearly be generalized to other complexity classes: a problem L is complete for a class \mathcal{C} if and only if \overline{L} is complete for $\text{co}\mathcal{C}$. In approaching the subject of quantum proof systems for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$, we would naturally like, first of all, to connect $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$ with a fundamental complexity class of quantum verifications like \mathcal{QMA} . However Theorem 18 deals with decision problems, whereas bounded error complexity classes are more naturally regarded as classes of promise problems: we don't know of any *language* complete for efficient quantum verifications (see [11]).

So as a first step we need to define a promise problem class $\text{co}\mathcal{QMA}$: what do we mean for the co operator, when applied to a *promise problem* class?

9.1 Definitions

It is natural to define the COMPLEMENT of a promise problem (L_y, L_n) as the promise problem (L_n, L_y) ; i.e., with the same promise and exchanged yes/no sets L_y, L_n . When the promise problem is simply denoted by L , we shall denote by \overline{L} its complement. In the following, when we speak of any complexity class, we implicitly intend it to be a class of promise problems.

If we define the class $\text{co}\mathcal{C}$ as the class of promise problems whose complement is in \mathcal{C} , then the co operator behaves analogously to how it does for classes of decision problems: or rather, the latter can be thought as a special case. In particular²²

$$\text{co}(\text{co}\mathcal{C}) = \mathcal{C} \tag{9.1}$$

and²³

$$(\mathcal{C} \subseteq \text{co}\mathcal{C}) \Leftrightarrow (\mathcal{C} \supseteq \text{co}\mathcal{C}) \tag{9.2}$$

Note also that, since $(L_y, L_n) \in \mathcal{P}$ simply means that the sets L_y, L_n can be distinguished in polynomial time, it is clear that

$$\text{co}\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{P}$$

But a class \mathcal{C} defined in terms of *verification procedures* might not be closed under complement: $\text{co}\mathcal{C}$ and \mathcal{C} can in general be distinct classes (incomparable, because of (9.2)).

²²

$$\begin{aligned} (L_y, L_n) \in \text{co}(\text{co}\mathcal{C}) &\Leftrightarrow (L_n, L_y) \in \text{co}\mathcal{C} \\ &\Leftrightarrow (L_y, L_n) \in \mathcal{C} \end{aligned}$$

²³ Assume

$$(\mathcal{C} \subseteq \text{co}\mathcal{C})$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} (L_y, L_n) \in \text{co}(\mathcal{C}) &\Rightarrow (L_n, L_y) \in (\mathcal{C}) \\ &\Rightarrow (L_n, L_y) \in \text{co}(\mathcal{C}) \\ &\Rightarrow (L_y, L_n) \in (\mathcal{C}) \end{aligned}$$

i.e.

$$(\mathcal{C} \supseteq \text{co}(\mathcal{C}))$$

(and since (9.1) we have also the reverse implication).

For coQMA , in order to better grasp the involved role of all the different elements, it may be worth explicitly casting the following.

Definition 19. We denote by coQMA the class of promise problems (L_y, L_n) such that, given an l -length instance of (L_y, L_n) , there is a quantum circuit C_l made of $\mathcal{O}(l^{c_1})$ gates, for some constant c_1 , such that, denoting by $C_l(f, \xi)$ the probabilistic final answer of C_l on input $|f\rangle|\xi\rangle$, conditions 1 and 2 are respected.

1. *Soundness:* $f \in L_y$ implies that $C_l(f, \xi)$ is ‘no’ with probability $\leq a$ for some $a(l)$ and whatever $|\xi\rangle$.
2. *Completeness:* $f \in L_n$ implies that $C_l(f, \xi)$ is ‘no’ with probability $\geq a + 1/l^{c_2}$ for some constant c_2 and at least one $|\xi\rangle$. \blacklozenge

The difference with QMA amounts to a switch of the universal and existential requirements²⁴ (soundness and completeness) for L_y, L_n . For a QMA verification procedure accepting is complete, and sound within the promise; in coQMA it is the opposite: rejecting is sound and complete. A coQMA verifier accepts, with bounded error, any $f \in L_y$; so any rejected f within the promise is, with bounded error, really a $f \in L_n$. Unless a valid refutation $|\xi\rangle$ is provided, also a $f \in L_n$ can be accepted, even with certainty, by a coQMA verifier, but a valid quantum refutation $|\xi\rangle$ always exists²⁵.

Several QMA -complete problems are known [11]. Let us take the most studied one, the local Hamiltonian problem (LH), and explicitly state its complement. It is sufficient here to restrict LH to projector operators, which gives us a quantum analogue of the maximum satisfiability problem.

Definition 20. We denote by $\overline{\text{MAX}k\text{QSAT}}_c$ the promise problem where the input is a set $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$ of k -local projectors on an n -qubit register, along with a real parameter ε , and it is asked whether

$$\varepsilon_{\min} \geq \varepsilon + n^{-c} \quad (L_y)$$

or

$$\varepsilon_{\min} \leq \varepsilon \quad (L_n) \quad \blacklozenge$$

Where ε_{\min} denotes the least eigenvalue of $\sum_{i=1}^s p_i$.

Note that we have

$$\overline{\text{MAX}k'\text{QSAT}}_{c'} \supseteq \overline{\text{MAX}k\text{QSAT}}_c$$

for every

$$k' \geq k \quad c' \geq c$$

It's well known [4] that $\overline{\text{MAX}k\text{QSAT}}_c$ (the complement of Definition 20, not usually denoted in some compact notation) is in QMA for every constant k, c (we can even let $k = \mathcal{O}(\log_2(n))$), and QMA -hard²⁶ for $k \geq 5, c \geq 0$. We will show in the next subsection that, as a result, $\overline{\text{MAX}5\text{QSAT}}_0$ and all the larger $\overline{\text{MAX}k\text{QSAT}}_c$ problems are coQMA -complete, and $\text{coQMA} = \text{QMA}$ iff $\overline{\text{MAX}5\text{QSAT}}_0 \in \text{QMA}$.

²⁴A quantum analogue of the whole polynomial hierarchy has been defined in [21]. It is not known whether the hierarchy would collapse in case $\text{coQMA} = \text{QMA}$.

²⁵With a number of qubits at most polynomial in l , since the verifying circuit only has $\mathcal{O}(l^{c_1})$ gates.

²⁶Usually the hardness result is stated for the more general LH problem. But if one examines the standard 5-local reduction, finds that it applies more specifically to projector instances. Moreover, note that a promise gap growing linearly with the number s of terms is often referred to as ‘‘constant’’, because of a (natural) normalization $1/s$ of the single terms. For such a gap the problem is not known to be (QMA) -hard: it is a *conjecture*, equivalent to a quantum version of PCP [3].

9.2 Generalization of the Cook–Reckhow Theorem

We refer to the elementary ‘Theorem 1’ in the influential paper [16] by Cook and Reckhow, which they take as the main motivation for the subsequent study of proof lengths in propositional logic. The theorem states exactly as follows: ‘The class \mathcal{NP} is closed under complement if and only if there exists a super proof system for the tautologies’. The unsatisfiability problem is equivalent to tautologies, for what concerns complexity; and the existence of a super proof system means $\overline{\text{SAT}} \in \mathcal{NP}$. We will here reformulate the theorem for the class \mathcal{QMA} .

Let us assume the promise problem C is \mathcal{QMA} -complete:

$$(C \in \mathcal{P}) \Leftrightarrow (\mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{P})$$

Then we have the following.

Lemma 21.

$$(\overline{C} \in \mathcal{P}) \Leftrightarrow (\text{co}\mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{P})$$

Proof. Consider a generic promise problem $(L_y, L_n) \in \text{co}\mathcal{QMA}$, then we have by definition

$$(L_n, L_y) \in \mathcal{QMA}$$

And (L_n, L_y) can be efficiently reduced to C , for the latter is by hypothesis \mathcal{QMA} -complete. I.e. instances of (L_n, L_y) are transformed by the reduction into instances of C , thus instances of (L_y, L_n) are transformed into instances of \overline{C} . If we can solve the latter (within the promise) in polynomial time, the same we can do with (L_y, L_n) .

The above argument is conveniently rephrased without mentioning reductions, using in a more cheeky way the fact that \mathcal{P} is closed under complement:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{C} \in \mathcal{P} &\Leftrightarrow C \in \mathcal{P} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{P} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \text{co}\mathcal{QMA} = \text{co}\mathcal{P} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \text{co}\mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{P} \end{aligned}$$

■

Iff C is \mathcal{QMA} -complete, then \overline{C} is $\text{co}\mathcal{QMA}$ -complete. Note that we can substitute \mathcal{BQP} for \mathcal{P} and all the above reasonings work in the same way:

$$(C \in \mathcal{BQP}) \Leftrightarrow (\mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{BQP}) \quad (\overline{C} \in \mathcal{BQP}) \Leftrightarrow (\text{co}\mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{BQP})$$

but completeness with respect to \mathcal{P} reductions is stronger.

This means (Theorem 22) that iff it exists an efficient quantum verification procedure for $\overline{\text{MAX5QSAT}}_0$, or for the complement of any other \mathcal{QMA} -complete problem, then the complement of *any* \mathcal{QMA} problem also belongs to \mathcal{QMA} .

Theorem 22 (Quantum Cook–Reckhow Theorem). *Let C be a \mathcal{QMA} -complete promise problem, then*

$$(\text{co}\mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{QMA}) \Leftrightarrow (\overline{C} \in \mathcal{QMA})$$

Proof. Of course if

$$\text{co}\mathcal{QMA} = \mathcal{QMA} \tag{9.3}$$

then

$$\overline{C} \in \mathcal{QMA} \tag{9.4}$$

Since by definition

$$\overline{C} \in \text{co}\mathcal{QMA}$$

In the other direction, assume (9.4). We have seen in the proof of Lemma 21 that every instance of a promise problem $L \in \text{co}\mathcal{QMA}$ can be reduced in polynomial time to an instance of \overline{C} . Then a \mathcal{QMA} verifier for L can just compute the reduction and then use the verification granted by (9.4). Thus $L \in \mathcal{QMA}$: i.e. $\text{co}\mathcal{QMA} \subseteq \mathcal{QMA}$. Which implies (9.3) because of (9.2). ■

Note also that, since \mathcal{BQP} is closed under complement and

$$\mathcal{BQP} \subseteq \mathcal{QMA} \cap \text{co}\mathcal{QMA}$$

it follows that

$$(\text{co}QMA \neq QMA) \Rightarrow (BQP \subset QMA)$$

Thus the foundational structure of a quantum version of proof complexity seems to naturally resemble the classical case. Although there are two immediate differences that we shall briefly address in the following subsections.

9.3 The Role of Promise

Let us assume that the promise problem (L_y, L_n) is complete for a class \mathcal{C} ; and consider a promise problem (L'_n, L'_y) , with $L'_n \supseteq L_n$ and $L'_y \supseteq L_y$: that is, the complement of (L_y, L_n) is a subproblem of (L'_n, L'_y) . Condition $(L'_n, L'_y) \in \mathcal{C}$ is stronger than $(L_n, L_y) \in \mathcal{C}$, so it would imply $\text{co}\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{C}$; then we would also have $(L'_y, L'_n) \in \mathcal{C}$.

Let's see this applied to our verification classes. It seems that we need a suitable promise to soundly verify that a given Hamiltonian has a ground state $|\Psi\rangle$ of sufficiently low energy²⁷. Should the complementary promise problem be efficiently verifiable under a weaker promise (within a larger promised space), then the promise could be correspondingly weakened also in the original problem: if we could, for example, efficiently verify the *unsatisfiability* of a quantum local formula without any promise, than there would also be a way to drop the promise in verifying satisfiability²⁸.

This strongly suggests that promise problem classes like QMA are not closed under complement: because the promise in, say, satisfiability appears tailored to the verification of satisfiability, but it has no apparent role in the verification of unsatisfiability. Thus, in comparison with $\overline{3SAT} \in \mathcal{NP}$, there is, due to the presence of the promise, a further element of arbitrariness in, say, hypothesizing $\overline{\text{MAX5QSAT}}_0 \in QMA$. Thus the quantum version of proof complexity has potentially an extra side of attack: one could prove $\text{co}QMA \neq QMA$ working on the promise gaps.

9.4 The Role of Error

The allowance of bounded error in accepting good certificates maps (via the quantum Cook–Levin theorem [27]) a QMA verifier to a frustrated Hamiltonian, that doesn't necessarily have $\varepsilon_{\min} = 0$. Then QSAT is not QMA -complete, unless $QMA = QMA_1$. Moreover, the class QMA_1 , since it contains a certainty requirement, could depend on the choice of the gate set used by the verifying circuits. In particular, a QMA_1 verification could be possible, with the given set of gates, only for p_i taken in a corresponding set of projectors. Let's denote by \mathfrak{p} the class of projectors such that, for $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s \in \mathfrak{p}$, a solution $|\Psi\rangle$ to system (2.7) can be efficiently verified with no error by a quantum circuit with gates from a standard set²⁹ \mathfrak{g} . Then we can explicitly write the following definitions, in a way such that they fit together.

²⁷For example, a QSAT instance can be infinitesimally “near” to satisfiability, without actually joining the class. So the natural verification process, which takes as a certificate an alleged eigenstate of 0 energy, and makes an energy measure on it, could give unsound answers if we don't match the bounded error requirement with an appropriate promise gap in the space of quantum formulas, separating those that are satisfiable from those *noticeably* unsatisfiable.

²⁸Note that this is not trivial, since a priori nothing forbids a promise problem and its complement to be in the same verification class with different promises.

²⁹A custom choice [30] is the universal set

$$\mathfrak{g} = \{\text{CNOT}, \text{H}, \text{R}(\pi/4)\}$$

with the classical

$$\text{CNOT} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Definition 23. We denote by coQMA_1 the class of promise problems (L_y, L_n) such that, given an l -length instance of (L_y, L_n) , there is a quantum circuit C_l made of $\mathcal{O}(l^{c_1})$ gates from the standard set \mathfrak{g} , for some constant c_1 , such that, denoting by $C_l(f, \xi)$ the probabilistic final answer of C_l on input $|f\rangle|\xi\rangle$, conditions 1 and 2 are respected.

1. *Soundness:* $f \in L_y$ implies that $C_l(f, \xi)$ is ‘no’ with probability $\leq 1 - 1/l^{c_2}$ for some constant c_2 and whatever $|\xi\rangle$.
2. *Completeness:* $f \in L_n$ implies that $C_l(f, \xi)$ is ‘no’ with certainty for at least one $|\xi\rangle$. \blacklozenge

Definition 24. We denote by $\overline{k\text{QSAT}}_c$ the promise problem where the input is a set $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s\}$ of k -local projectors on an n -qubit register, and it is asked whether

$$\varepsilon_{\min} \geq n^{-c} \tag{L_y}$$

or

$$(\varepsilon_{\min} = 0) \wedge \forall i (p_i \in \mathfrak{p}) \tag{L_n}$$

Where ε_{\min} denotes the least eigenvalue of $\sum_{i=1}^s p_i$. \blacklozenge

A coQMA_1 verifier can *reject* without error, given the right certificate; that’s why the restriction to \mathfrak{p} projectors is for the L_n case in Definition 24. Note that the complement of perfect completeness doesn’t give perfect soundness, at least not trivially. In any case we have of course

$$\text{QMA}_1 \subseteq \text{QMA} \qquad \text{coQMA}_1 \subseteq \text{coQMA}$$

Now, reasoning³⁰ as in Lemma 21, we have, since 3QSAT_0 is QMA_1 -complete, that $\overline{k\text{QSAT}}_c$ is coQMA_1 -complete for $k \geq 3, c \geq 0$. And, reasoning as in Theorem 22, that $\text{coQMA}_1 = \text{QMA}_1$ iff $\overline{3\text{QSAT}}_0 \in \text{QMA}_1$.

Finally, in a less strict case, should a QMA verification for quantum unsatisfiability exist: what could we conclude? The only thing we can trivially say is

$$(\text{coQMA}_1 \subseteq \text{QMA}) \Leftrightarrow (\text{QMA}_1 \subseteq \text{coQMA})$$

So, if $\overline{3\text{QSAT}}_0 \in \text{QMA}$, then $\text{QMA}_1, \text{coQMA}_1$ would both lie in $\text{QMA} \cap \text{coQMA}$; but it could still be $\text{QMA}_1 \neq \text{coQMA}_1$.

10 Conclusions

10.1 Classical Proof Systems

We have presented the first nontrivial proof systems for $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$.

The MC proof system works with local matrices expressed in form (2.4). We proved in Section 5.1 that, when the initial matrices are diagonal the system is equivalent to its restriction to only diagonal matrices (DMC); this subcase comprises $\overline{\text{SAT}}$ instances, represented naturally as diagonal projectors. We proved in Section 5.2 that DMC, and thus MC, is equivalent to Resolution on CNF instances.

If we allow matrices to be expressed as sums of terms with *different localities*, we obtain a stronger system: MC+ (Section 6). Even in this case, on diagonal instances the system is equivalent to its

the Hadamard gate

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

and the $\pi/4$ phase gate:

$$R(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\theta} \end{bmatrix}$$

³⁰Note that in the proofs of Lemma 21 and Theorem 22 the error requirements of the classes play no role.

diagonal restriction (DMC+). As a proof that MC+ is strictly stronger than MC, we have shown that DMC+ is equivalent to Polynomial Calculus with Resolution (which is known to be strictly stronger than Resolution).

We don't explicitly show it, but it's straightforward to define a third system, less powerful than MC+ but incomparable with MC, by limiting MC+ to not use the \tilde{x}_i operators (they can always be substituted by $1 - x_i$). This system on diagonal instances is equivalent to the basic Polynomial Calculus (PC) with Boolean axioms. Furthermore, in the MC+ setting it is natural to also consider the static proof systems: because, unlike in MC, we are no longer required to expand matrices across different localities in order to add them, making static proofs of the type (5.1) efficiently verifiable. If we further restrict static MC+ to diagonal matrices, using only the x_i operators, we have a classical system equivalent to the original Nullstellensatz proof system [8].

These matricial systems thus enable, when applied on classical logic, to frame Resolution and algebraic proof systems in a unified purview. But their main reason of interest is, in our opinion, that they allow the study of the complexity of classical and quantum formulas through unified systems, using the same syntactic rules to prove classical as well as quantum inferences. Clearly, we can apply the system not only to sets of projectors, expressing quantum or classical properties: by Theorem 3, from any set of initial matrices, we can deduce any matrix whose nullspace contains their common nullspace. In particular, it can be used to prove that the initial matrices don't share a nontrivial common nullspace, deducing 1. If locality isn't n , verifying such a proof can be significantly faster than computing the nullspace directly, or solving the system for ideal membership.

We think that further studies of these matricial systems may start by trying to generalize to the quantum case well-known results about Polynomial Calculus and Resolution. An example of this straightforward approach was presented in Section 7, where we extended a classical proof search algorithm for PC to general MC+ proofs.

10.2 Quantum Proof Systems

The matricial proof systems presented in this paper are classical, in that a proving certificate is a string that can be efficiently verified by a classical Turing machine.

There is no known way to profitably employ quantum states and quantum computation in proving unsatisfiability. In the classical case, nontrivial proof systems for the complements of constraint satisfaction problems do exist, in particular for $\overline{\text{SAT}}$, and are the object of scrutiny of proof complexity studies. Even if it is believed that no such proof system can do significantly better than a trivial truth table in some worst case ($\text{co}\mathcal{NP} \neq \mathcal{NP}$), classical certificates are surely useful on numerous instances. However, there is no apparent way to leverage the few quantum procedures that we currently know with problems like $\overline{\text{QSAT}}$.

Although one could legitimately feel that a really quantum calculus is to be more naturally and profitably applied to quantum formulas, since quantum computers directly manipulate quantum logical semantics. Maybe we can profitably encode more information in a quantum certificate: a full set of 2^n strings can be held in superposition in a single quantum state of length n , although it is well known that this cannot be *trivially* exploited (see for example [7]). Or maybe quantum computation allows for the efficient processing of a short certificate that would be cryptic for classical computers: quantum circuits can, for example, extract a private key from a public one exponentially faster than what we consider classical computation able to do (a good review on the subject is in [35]).

In Section 8, we explained why Pudlák's quantum Frege systems do not leverage the power

of quantum verification procedures. We are not able to give an example ourselves of a quantum proof system for classical or quantum logic problems ($\text{SAT}, \overline{\text{QSAT}}$), but we believe that further studies on the subject could lead to interesting insights in both proof complexity and quantum computation. We initiated a potential line of investigation in Section 9, where we carried out the minor technical adjustments needed in order to generalize for quantum verification classes the Cook–Reckhow approach to $\text{co}\mathcal{NP} \neq \mathcal{NP}$. And in Subsections 9.3, 9.4 we addressed the peculiarities of such a quantum version of classical proof complexity: in particular we noted how a tight definition of the promise gaps needed for local Hamiltonian problems could itself prove $\text{coQMA} \neq \text{QMA}$.

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